

Capable Destruction

Execution Economics and the Value Reversal Architecture of Australia's Robodebt Scheme

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Abstract

Why do technically capable organisations sometimes produce outcomes worse than inaction? This paper applies the Execution Economics (EE) framework to Australia's Robodebt scheme (2015–2019) to develop a structural answer. Working from the core identity $Y = d(P) \cdot S$ — where Y is realised outcomes, $d(P)$ is decision quality as a function of predictive capacity P , and S is decision sovereignty — the analysis identifies Robodebt as a canonical case of value reversal: the structural condition in which sovereignty is inverted, so that each increment of decision quality amplifies harm rather than reducing it. Three concurrent structural failures — sovereignty inversion, feedback suppression, and artificial deliberative congestion — together produced a net Commonwealth loss on the order of A\$565 million on the scheme's own operation, approximately A\$1.76 billion in unlawful debts raised against more than 500,000 Australians, documented human harm the Commission linked to suicide, and a sequence of Commonwealth liabilities that now includes the A\$112 million Prygodicz settlement approved in June 2021 and a proposed Knox appeal settlement of A\$548.5 million announced in September 2025 and pending Federal Court approval at a hearing scheduled for 22 June 2026. The scheme's technical efficiency was not a mitigating factor but the amplifier of institutional misalignment. Cross-case examination of the Dutch Toeslagenaffaire and the UK Post Office Horizon system establishes that the structural signature of value reversal generalises beyond the Australian context. Five governance design principles follow from the diagnosis, and the post-Robodebt Australian reform programme — the Administrative Review Tribunal, the re-established Administrative Review Council, the Australian Centre for Evaluation, and the Thodey capability-review architecture — is assessed for which elements of the value reversal architecture it reaches and which it does not.

Keywords: value reversal; execution economics; decision sovereignty; algorithmic governance; implementation failure; Robodebt; welfare administration; automated compliance; administrative law.

1. Introduction

Public administration theory has spent five decades building a sophisticated account of implementation failure. The canonical starting point is Pressman and Wildavsky's (1973) demonstration that the probability of successful policy implementation falls geometrically with the number of required approval sequences: with fifteen actors each holding a ninety-

five per cent compliance probability, the compound probability of full implementation falls below fifty per cent. Bardach (1977) extended this to show that implementation is properly understood as a game among actors with divergent interests, each capable of deflecting, delaying, or redefining original policy intent. Lipsky (1980) observed that frontline workers exercise the discretion that actually determines what government policy means in practice, translating statutes into experience through the accumulated pressures and shortcuts of high-caseload work. Each of these frameworks treats failure as degradation — execution that falls short of intent, drifts from it, or is captured by it.

None of them is equipped to explain what happened with Australia's Robodebt scheme.

Robodebt was not an implementation failure in any of these senses. It was, by the measures its designers valued, an implementation success. The Online Compliance Intervention (OCI) deployed by the Department of Human Services (DHS) from 2015 was technically efficient: it processed welfare compliance cases at a scale and speed that manual review had never approached, generating automated debt notices across hundreds of thousands of accounts with minimal human involvement. Its institutional sponsors — ministers, senior officials, Cabinet — approved, supported, and defended it. Oversight mechanisms formally existed. The system executed faithfully what it was designed to execute. The outcome was the destruction of approximately A\$565 million of net Commonwealth value on the scheme's own operation, the generation of approximately A\$1.76 billion in unlawful debts against more than 500,000 Australians, documented harm to the mental health and financial stability of hundreds of thousands of recipients, linkage on the Commission's evidence to documented suicides, and a sequence of Commonwealth liabilities whose total exposure remains open at the time of writing: approximately A\$751 million in refunds undertaken in 2020, an A\$112 million class-action settlement approved in *Prygodicz (No. 2) [2021] FCA 634* on 11 June 2021, and a proposed A\$548.5 million Knox appeal settlement announced in September 2025 and scheduled for Federal Court approval at a hearing on 22 June 2026, which if approved would constitute the largest class-action settlement in Australian legal history (Attorney-General's Department, 2025; Gordon Legal, 2025; Services Australia, 2026; Holmes, 2023).

This is not degradation toward zero. It is execution in the wrong direction. The distinction matters analytically, because it calls for a different theoretical category and a different remedial logic. Conventional implementation theory prescribes tightening the chain of execution — reducing veto points, strengthening accountability, improving information flow. Applied to Robodebt, these prescriptions would have accelerated the harm. A scheme with fewer veto points, stronger accountability to performance metrics, and tighter information flow from debt recovery operations to ministerial offices would have raised more unlawful debts faster. That this inversion is not intuitive to existing theory is the intellectual problem the present paper addresses.

The Decision Sovereignty framework introduced by Fritz, Fritz-Kalish and Bodrova (2025) supplies the analytical category that public administration theory has lacked: value reversal. Its core identity:

$$Y = d(P) \cdot S$$

where Y denotes realised outcomes, $d(P)$ represents decision quality as a function of predictive capacity P , and S denotes decision sovereignty (signed). The identity contains a prediction no adjacent theory makes explicitly: when S is negative, raising $d(P)$ makes outcomes worse. A more capable system executing in the wrong direction does more damage than an incapable one. The scheme's technical competence was not a countervailing factor; it was the amplifier.

This paper applies Execution Economics to Robodebt as an explanatory and theoretical case study with four objectives. First, to demonstrate the analytical utility of value reversal as a distinct category, distinguishing it rigorously from conventional implementation failure. Second, to trace the three structural pathways — sovereignty inversion, feedback suppression, and artificial deliberative congestion — through which Robodebt arrived at negative transmission. Third, to show how the removal of street-level discretion in a misaligned system does not correct misalignment but eliminates the one institutional mechanism capable of generating error-correcting signals at the point of implementation. Fourth, to derive design principles for algorithmic governance that follow from the structural diagnosis rather than from generalised injunctions about oversight, and to use those principles to evaluate the post-Robodebt Australian reform programme.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 sets out the theoretical framework, distinguishing value reversal from conventional implementation failure and situating Execution Economics within the existing public administration literature. Section 3 describes the research methodology, including the alternative explanations considered and rejected. Section 4 provides the factual and institutional account of Robodebt. Section 5 conducts the EE analysis of its structural components. Section 6 addresses the persistence problem and the paradox of capable destruction jointly. Section 7 examines the cross-case signature of value reversal. Section 8 derives governance design implications and evaluates the post-Robodebt reform programme against them. Section 9 specifies falsification conditions and acknowledges limitations. Section 10 concludes.

2. Theoretical Framework: Execution Economics and Value Reversal

2.1 The core identity and its structural logic

Execution Economics models realised outcomes through a multiplicative identity, $Y = d(P) \cdot S$, in which Y denotes realised outcomes; $d(P)$ represents decision quality as a function of predictive capacity P ; and S denotes decision sovereignty — the signed capacity of the institutional architecture to convert decisions into outcomes. The multiplicative form is not a modelling convenience. Fritz and Fritz-Kalish (2026) derive it from three axioms. Sovereignty necessity requires that $S = 0$ implies $Y = 0$ regardless of $d(P)$: an institution with no effective transmission capacity produces no outcomes, however good its decisions. Decision necessity requires that $d(P) = 0$ implies $Y = 0$ regardless of S : an institution with no decision capacity produces no outcomes, however capable its transmission. Separability requires that $d(P)$ and S are independently determined, ruling out nested forms. The first axiom eliminates additive alternatives; the third eliminates compositional alternatives. The multiplicative form follows uniquely.

The signed character of S is the feature that distinguishes this framework from existing performance models. Conventional performance theory treats execution as a positive variable that can be more or less, better or worse, but always in the same direction as intent. Execution Economics permits S to take negative values, which occurs when the executing organisation is systematically oriented against its stated objective. The practical implication is severe: when S is negative, raising decision quality multiplies harm rather than reducing it. The organisation's competence becomes the mechanism of harm. A formal statement of this amplification condition is given in Appendix B.

2.2 Decision sovereignty as a compound variable

Decision sovereignty is itself a compound variable. In the framework's operational specification, S combines three elements: the effective authority of actors who hold decision rights, the institutional machinery through which those rights are exercised, and the alignment of operative objectives with stated objectives across the principal hierarchy. The sign of S is determined by the sovereignty-weighted sum of individual actor alignments: where the actors with greatest effective authority are oriented toward the stated mission, S is positive; where they are systematically oriented against it, S is negative.

This construction extends the standard principal–agent model in two analytically important ways. First, it treats misalignment as signed rather than merely degraded. In the canonical agency formulation (Eisenhardt, 1989), agents diverge from principals in the sense of shirking, slack, or partial capture — degrees of falling short. Execution Economics recognises that agents can actively reverse principal objectives, not merely fail to achieve them. Second, the framework recognises that in complex institutional settings there are multiple layered principals — ministers, Cabinet, Parliament, the public — whose alignment orientations must be weighted by their effective decision authority rather than their formal constitutional position. This construction resonates with Miller's (2005) analysis of hierarchical agency under political control and with Wood and Waterman's (1991) demonstration that bureaucratic responsiveness tracks operative rather than formal principal–agent relations. Where these literatures stop short of formalising sign reversal, Execution Economics makes the reversal condition explicit.

Two further structural factors modulate the magnitude of harm under negative sovereignty. Institutional capacity K determines how much decision load the system can absorb before congesting. Congestion — the ratio of decision load to capacity — exhibits a phase-transition property: below a critical threshold, delays scale proportionately; near the threshold, small increments produce disproportionate breakdown; above it, decisions queue without resolution. Crucially, artificial suppression of deliberative congestion — forcing decisions through institutional channels faster than their natural equilibration rate — does not reduce the informational demands of those decisions; it eliminates the error-correction that slow deliberation would have provided. The formal congestion function is developed in Appendix A.

2.3 Value reversal versus implementation failure

The distinction between conventional implementation failure and value reversal has direct consequences for institutional diagnosis and remedial design. Implementation failure, as

understood from Pressman and Wildavsky (1973) through the subsequent four decades of literature, is a problem of degradation: execution falls short of intent. The organisation intends a positive outcome; delivery friction, coordination failures, veto actors, and resource constraints mean that only a fraction of the intended outcome is realised. The remedial logic follows: reduce friction, reduce veto points, strengthen coordination, improve resources.

Value reversal is a different structural condition. The problem is not that execution falls short of intent but that execution is oriented against a stated intent that was itself a misrepresentation of the operative objectives of the controlling actors. The remedial logic is correspondingly inverted. Reducing friction in this condition accelerates harm. Strengthening accountability to performance metrics deepens alignment with the wrong objectives. Improving analytical capacity enables more precise and efficient harm generation. Robodebt demonstrates each of these perverse dynamics.

Bovens and Zouridis (2002) identified the precursor concept in their analysis of system-level bureaucracy — administrative systems in which algorithms replace street-level discretion entirely, fundamentally altering the accountability architecture of public administration. Their insight was that replacing street-level bureaucrats with rule systems does not eliminate the values embedded in those rules; it embeds them more deeply and removes the human discretion that had previously served as a corrective mechanism. They did not, however, formalise the condition under which this leads not merely to rigid implementation but to active harm amplification. Bovens (2007) subsequently developed an influential account of public accountability as a relationship in which an actor must explain and justify conduct to a forum that may impose consequences, but that account too stops short of the sign-reversal question: it specifies what accountability is rather than what happens when its feedback loops are architecturally severed. Execution Economics provides the missing formalisation through the value reversal prediction, and in doing so supplies the structural vocabulary through which algorithmic governance can be diagnosed rather than merely lamented.

2.4 Situating Execution Economics in the broader literature

Execution Economics engages and extends several established bodies of research. Implementation theory (Pressman and Wildavsky, 1973; Bardach, 1977; Mazmanian and Sabatier, 1983) demonstrated that execution is where policy fails, showing that the compound probability of successful implementation across multiple decision nodes declines geometrically. What implementation theory cannot resolve — and what the Robodebt case makes visible — is the functional form of the relationship between institutional conditions and outcomes, and the prediction of when raising decision quality worsens results. The multiplicative identity supplies this through S and its decomposition: each condition identified in implementation theory acquires structural content, and the sign-reversal prediction the implementation literature lacks becomes a formal consequence.

Incomplete contracts theory, developed in the Grossman–Hart–Moore tradition and synthesised in Hart's (2017) Nobel lecture and Aghion and Holden's (2011) survey, grounds the sovereignty construct's treatment of residual decision rights. Because no

institutional arrangement can specify in advance how every contingency should be resolved, governance designs must allocate authority over contingencies that contracts and procedures cannot anticipate. In private-sector applications, residual rights of control are tied to asset ownership; in public-sector applications, they inhere in the principal hierarchy. The framework's sovereignty-weighting methodology (Appendix C) operationalises residual decision rights for public-sector settings, with the added step of assigning each set of rights a sign according to the operative alignment of the actors who hold them. Where incomplete contracts theory asks who should hold residual authority, the present framework asks in which direction that authority is oriented — the question that becomes dispositive under conditions of negative sovereignty.

Absorptive capacity theory (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990) and dynamic capabilities theory (Teece, Pisano and Shuen, 1997) both operate on the input side of the decision process: the first explains which organisations benefit from new information or technology; the second privileges the ability to sense, seize, and transform. Neither accounts for what happens when learning is high but execution is inverted. Robodebt illustrates precisely this: DHS's analytical capability was not negligible, and the system was designed and implemented with institutional sophistication. What determined the outcome was not the quality of learning but the direction of institutional alignment. The sign function applied to sovereignty closes this gap.

Principal–agent theory (Eisenhardt, 1989; Miller, 2005) maps most directly onto the sovereignty-weight problem. In principal–agent models, the agent's behaviour diverges from the principal's preferences when incentive structures are misaligned or when information asymmetry permits the agent to conceal divergence. Robodebt is, in principal–agent terms, a case of severe information asymmetry: senior DHS officials held information about the scheme's legal infirmity that was not available to the principals — ministers, Cabinet — through channels the agents themselves controlled. Gailmard and Patty (2013) develop the information–expertise trade-off further, showing that principals face a structural dilemma in which the agents they rely on for expertise are the same agents whose discretion they seek to constrain. The sovereignty-weighted alignment construct extends these models by treating misalignment as signed rather than degraded, and by distributing weight across multiple layered principals.

Scott's (1998) Seeing Like a State identifies legibility-driven harm as a general risk of high-modern administration: schemes that impose legible categories on populations whose circumstances resist those categories produce systematic harm not through malice but through the mismatch between schema and lived particularity. Income averaging is a paradigmatic Scottian legibility device. The structural prediction the present framework adds is when that harm is amplified rather than contained: legibility combined with negative sovereignty and high execution efficiency produces the value reversal configuration.

The AI and algorithmic administration literatures offer complementary engagement. Agrawal, Gans and Goldfarb (2018) demonstrated that AI reduces the cost of prediction and increases decision volume, but cannot predict why those decisions so often fail to improve outcomes in the public sector. The EE mechanism supplies an answer: AI raises $d(P)$ and increases decision load; when load exceeds capacity and alignment is not

verified before deployment, the productivity paradox becomes a structural prediction rather than an empirical puzzle. Diakopoulos (2016), Citron and Pasquale (2014), and Pasquale (2015) identify algorithmic opacity as the central accountability problem in public administration. O'Neil (2016) documented across multiple domains how optimisation against misspecified objectives generates discriminatory and self-reinforcing harm at scale — a diagnosis Leigh (2022) explicitly invoked in parliamentary commentary on Robodebt. Eubanks (2018) showed, with particular force for welfare contexts, how automation systematically disadvantages populations already structurally disadvantaged. Zarsky (2016) proposed 'transparent predictions' — the obligation to disclose algorithmic methodologies to those subject to them — as a precondition for meaningful contestation. These concerns share a structural source: opacity, the absence of due process, and the suppression of transparency are not accidental features of algorithmic administration but institutional consequences of alignment failure at the principal hierarchy level. When operative objectives are oriented toward volume rather than accuracy, transparency is a threat rather than a design criterion, because transparency would expose the gap between stated and operative intent.

Reputation-based accounts of bureaucracy (Carpenter, 2001, 2010; Carpenter and Krause, 2012) provide the final theoretical engagement, developed in detail in Section 6. Carpenter identifies four dimensions of bureaucratic reputation — performative, moral, procedural, and technical. Public agencies cultivate different dimensions for different audiences, and reputational defence along any dimension can operate as an operative objective distinct from, and in conflict with, stated mission. The condition under which such cultivation becomes structurally harmful is precisely the value reversal configuration: when reputational defence displaces the stated mission as the operative objective and is combined with high execution efficiency and suppressed feedback.

Execution Economics sits in direct dialogue with a distinctively Australian line of recent economic-diagnostic work on Commonwealth policy failure. Holden and Leigh (2022) analysed Australia's comparatively slow Covid-19 vaccine rollout through the instruments of portfolio diversification, option value, and dynamic optimisation, estimating that optimal procurement could have averted at least A\$31 billion in economic damage. Their diagnostic identifies policy error as a failure of decision quality under uncertainty — in EE terms, a failure on the $d(P)$ axis. What their instruments are not designed to supply is an account of why otherwise capable institutions apply the wrong tools, or why internal correction processes do or do not engage when adverse signals emerge. The vaccine rollout and Robodebt are instructive precisely in their divergence. Both involved Commonwealth agencies capable of sophisticated analytical work; the vaccine rollout was substantially corrected within twelve months of sustained political pressure, whereas Robodebt persisted for four and a half years against comparable pressure. A portfolio-theoretic or optimisation-based diagnosis cannot account for that difference. The present framework can: the Robodebt principal hierarchy had operative objectives structurally aligned against correction (debt volume, budget savings, reputational defence of the scheme's integrity), whereas the vaccine rollout's principal hierarchy did not. Leigh (2022, 2023), separately in parliamentary and public commentary, identified several of the structural features the framework formalises: that Robodebt 'essentially emerged from a political necessity' of propping up the budget bottom line rather than from accurate

compliance objectives; that what distinguished it from prior income-averaging exercises was the removal of the human review loop; and that its principal lesson concerns 'how to use automation well from an instance in which automation has clearly been used very badly'.

None of these adjacent theories would have predicted what happened, because each lacks either the signed sovereignty variable, the congestion formalisation, or the multi-principal alignment architecture needed to diagnose value reversal before it materialises at scale. Taken together, they supply the empirical and conceptual field into which the framework's structural predictions are embedded.

3. Methodology

3.1 Case selection and research design

This paper employs qualitative single-case methodology applied to Australia's Robodebt scheme as a critical case (Yin, 2018; Seawright and Gerring, 2008). Case selection followed the logic of the critical case design. Robodebt is selected not as a representative instance of algorithmic governance failure — its scale and the exceptional depth of the Royal Commission's evidentiary record make it unusual — but as a case in which the theoretical predictions of Execution Economics are most stringently testable. A critical case is one where, if the theory does not explain the outcome, confidence in the theory is substantially reduced; where it does explain the outcome with precision, the explanatory gain is correspondingly high (Yin, 2018, p. 51). Robodebt meets this criterion. The Commission's evidentiary record is extensive enough to assess each structural variable in the framework with some precision, and the outcome — net value destruction at scale despite high technical capability — is exactly the class of outcome that the value reversal prediction is designed to explain, and that no adjacent theory handles adequately.

The single-case design is appropriate for three reasons. First, the theoretical contribution advanced — the formalisation of value reversal as a distinct analytical category — requires demonstration in a case where the category's defining features are present and observable, not estimation across a population in which such cases may be rare or incompletely documented. Second, the Royal Commission's Final Report (Holmes, 2023) provides an evidentiary base of exceptional depth: 958,000 documents examined, 115 witnesses heard across 303 hours of hearings, 1,099 public submissions received, and findings carrying the status of judicially supervised inquiry (Royal Commission into the Robodebt Scheme, 2023). This affords triangulation across documentary, testimonial, and institutional evidence that substantially mitigates the generalisability limitation inherent in single-case designs (Seawright and Gerring, 2008, p. 295). Third, the framework's variables — sovereignty, feedback architecture, congestion, execution efficiency — admit qualitative assessment from institutional evidence without requiring the panel data that causal identification through quantitative methods would demand.

3.2 Evidentiary triangulation

The primary data source is Holmes (2023). To mitigate the monoculture risk inherent in reliance on a single authoritative source, the analysis triangulates against five independent bodies of evidence. The Commonwealth Ombudsman's 2017 review (Commonwealth Ombudsman, 2017) provides a contemporaneous institutional assessment predating the Royal Commission. The Senate Community Affairs References Committee's 2017 inquiry (Senate Community Affairs References Committee, 2017) generated independent testimonial evidence from affected individuals and welfare organisations. The published scholarly record — Whiteford (2021), Priergaard (2025), Ng and O'Sullivan (2023), Hannah and Botterill (2025), and Henman (2025) — engages the evidence independently of the Commission's framing. Gordon Legal's class-action proceedings and the resulting judicial record (*Prygodicz v Commonwealth* (No. 2) [2021] FCA 634; Gordon Legal, 2025) supply an adversarial evidentiary pathway that compelled discovery of documents the implementing agency had filtered from internal processes. Leigh (2022) supplies parliamentary and constituent testimony from a sitting member of the House of Representatives with direct portfolio responsibility.

Where these sources conflict with Holmes (2023) — notably, the Ombudsman's 2017 finding that the scheme was operating acceptably, which the Royal Commission subsequently found was based on incomplete information provided by DHS — the conflict is noted and its evidentiary implications addressed. The Ombudsman's 2017 finding is treated not as counter-evidence to the Commission's conclusions but as direct evidence of feedback suppression: an oversight institution reaching a favourable conclusion on the basis of agency-curated information is precisely what Execution Economics predicts in a value reversal configuration. This evidentiary move is important for the paper's analytical warrant: the existence of apparently contradictory source material is, in a value reversal case, itself confirmatory rather than disconfirmatory, because feedback suppression is a predicted feature of the condition being diagnosed.

3.3 Process tracing and inference warrant

Analysis proceeds through process tracing: identifying the causal mechanisms through which the observed outcome was produced, step by step, with each step grounded in the Commission's evidence (Beach and Pedersen, 2013, p. 1). The three structural pathways — sovereignty inversion, feedback suppression, and artificial deliberative congestion — are the output of this tracing exercise, not prior theoretical impositions on the data. Inference follows Beach and Pedersen's (2013, pp. 100–104) typology. The Commission's documentation of the December 2014 legal advice being excluded from Cabinet documentation functions as a smoking-gun test for the feedback-suppression mechanism: its presence is sufficient to confirm the mechanism, and its absence would have been sufficient to reject it. The convergence of performance-metric evidence from the Royal Commission, the Senate Committee, the scholarly literature, and ministerial commentary on the same operative-objective finding functions as a doubly decisive test for sovereignty inversion: multiple independent sources, each capable of producing a disconfirming finding, instead produce convergent confirmation.

Decision Sovereignty Index (DSI) component estimates in Section 5.5 are derived explicitly from the Commission's evidentiary findings; the mapping from Commission findings to component values, and the computation of the composite index, are set out in Appendix D for scrutiny and revision. The paper does not claim causal identification in the econometric sense. It claims structural diagnosis — the identification of the institutional configuration that produced the observed outcome — which is the appropriate epistemic standard for qualitative case analysis of this type (Beach and Pedersen, 2013). Where the Commission's findings are ambiguous or contested, the ambiguity is noted.

3.4 Alternative explanations considered and rejected

Rigorous single-case analysis requires explicit consideration of rival explanations for the observed outcome. Four alternatives merit serious consideration.

Individual malfeasance. The hypothesis that Robodebt's outcome is principally explained by the misconduct of specific individuals — the officials who suppressed the 2014 legal advice, the ministers who defended the scheme in the face of mounting evidence of its unlawfulness — has the virtue that the Commission found individual misconduct and made referrals whose merits the National Anti-Corruption Commission subsequently assessed, finding that two of six referred individuals engaged in serious corrupt conduct (NACC, 2026). The hypothesis nonetheless fails as a structural account. Individual misconduct does not explain why formally identical institutional architectures (the Commonwealth Ombudsman, the AAT, the Senate committee system) systematically failed to generate correction; nor why the scheme persisted across changes in departmental leadership and ministerial responsibility; nor why comparable value reversal configurations arose in entirely different national settings (the Dutch Toeslagenaffaire, the UK Post Office Horizon system) in the absence of any common individuals. Individual misconduct is an element of the Robodebt case but not an adequate explanation of it.

Technical failure. The hypothesis that Robodebt was a technical failure — a software or data-matching error that could have been corrected by better code — is directly contradicted by the Commission's evidence. The income-averaging methodology functioned as designed; its outputs were technically what the specification called for. The failure was in the relationship between the methodology and the statutory framework under which the scheme purported to operate. Calling this a technical failure inverts cause and effect: the methodology was not flawed because of a technical error; the technical design implemented a methodology that was flawed at the legal-institutional level.

Resource constraint. The hypothesis that Robodebt's persistence is explained by resource constraints in DHS — insufficient staffing to conduct manual review, insufficient funding for alternative compliance approaches — has surface plausibility, given the Commonwealth's concurrent programme of public-service staffing caps. It fails on close examination. The scheme's design actively removed the human review that resource constraints might plausibly explain away, and the automation that replaced it was specifically chosen for its cost-per-case advantages. Resource constraint may help explain the political attraction of automation; it does not explain why the automation was oriented against the stated compliance mission, which is the sovereignty-inversion question.

Pure implementation failure. The fourth alternative — that Robodebt is best understood through the conventional implementation-failure lens as a case of policy intent corrupted by execution friction — is the explanation Execution Economics is designed to reject, and the rejection is testable. If Robodebt were a degradation case, lower execution efficiency, higher discretion, and stronger feedback channels would have produced better outcomes; the framework predicts they would have produced better outcomes only conditional on positive sovereignty. The 2019 Commonwealth Solicitor-General opinion — which reiterated, verbatim in substance, the conclusion of the 2014 DSS advice — forecloses the degradation hypothesis: the stated intent (accurate compliance under the Social Security Act) and the operative intent (debt volume, budget repair, scheme-integrity defence) diverged from inception. This is not execution falling short of intent; it is execution faithfully serving an intent different from the stated one.

Each alternative is considered, engaged with the evidence, and found insufficient. The value reversal diagnosis is advanced not because it is the only possible explanation but because it is the explanation that accommodates the evidence most comprehensively and survives the comparative tests in Section 7 that the alternatives cannot.

4. The Robodebt Scheme: Institutional Account

4.1 Origins and design logic

The origins of the Online Compliance Intervention lie in the Budget preparation cycle of 2014–2015. Officers of the Customer Compliance Branch of the Department of Human Services developed proposals for automated welfare compliance as part of a broader departmental response to ministerial interest in savings measures. The core innovation of the resulting system was a data-matching methodology: annual income data reported by welfare recipients to the Australian Taxation Office (ATO) would be matched against fortnightly Centrelink payment records. Where the averaged ATO data suggested a higher income than the Centrelink records assumed, the system would automatically generate a debt notice requiring the recipient to demonstrate that no overpayment had occurred.

The critical and fundamental flaw was income averaging. The methodology took annual income figures from ATO records and divided them by twenty-six to estimate average fortnightly income. For any recipient whose income was irregular across the year — seasonal workers, casual employees, students, people moving in and out of employment — this produced systematically false results. A seasonal worker earning forty thousand dollars across four months of work would appear, under this methodology, to have earned approximately fifteen hundred dollars per fortnight throughout the year, including fortnights in which they earned nothing and legitimately received welfare payments. The averaged figure exceeded the threshold; a debt notice was generated.

Before the scheme was finalised for Budget approval, legal advice from the Department of Social Services (DSS) concluded, in December 2014, that the income-averaging methodology did not comply with the Social Security Act 1991 (Cth). The Act requires that income assessments be based on actual fortnightly income, not on annual averages. This advice was not included in the New Policy Proposal documentation submitted to Cabinet

for approval. The scheme was announced in the 2015–16 Budget as part of the Strengthening the Integrity of Welfare Payments measure and commenced in pilot form in April 2015 (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 3). Hannah and Botterill (2025) document in detail how legal advice was systematically siloed from policy-design processes throughout the scheme's life, with non-lawyers strategically shaping the wording of requests for advice to obtain answers compatible with pre-formed policy positions.

4.2 Scale, mechanism, and financial consequences

The scheme scaled rapidly from its pilot phase. By the time it was abandoned in November 2019 — following a 2019 Commonwealth Solicitor-General opinion that concluded, in terms identical to the 2014 advice, that the methodology was unlawful — it had generated automated debt notices against more than 500,000 welfare recipients. The Royal Commission documented the financial consequences in detail (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 14), summarised in Table 1, with subsequent class-action settlement and appeal figures (Prygodicz v Commonwealth (No. 2) [2021] FCA 634; Attorney-General's Department, 2025; Gordon Legal, 2025; Services Australia, 2026) added to capture the full financial envelope at the time of writing.

Metric	Figure
Unlawful debts raised	Approximately A\$1.76 billion
Individuals affected	More than 500,000 welfare recipients
Projected Budget savings	A\$4.772 billion (2014–15 to 2021–22)
Actual savings delivered	A\$406.196 million (approximately 8.5 cents per dollar projected)
Total scheme operating costs	A\$971.391 million
Net cost to Commonwealth (scheme alone)	Approximately A\$565.195 million
Debts cancelled and refunds paid	A\$1.763 billion (including approximately A\$751 million refunded)
Prygodicz (No. 2) settlement, approved 11 June 2021	A\$112 million distributed to approximately 394,000 group members
Knox appeal settlement (proposed September 2025; pending Federal Court approval on 22 June 2026; registration window closed 6 March 2026)	A\$548.5 million total, including A\$475 million in additional compensation; if approved, the largest class-action settlement in Australian legal history
Duration of active operation	April 2015 – November 2019 (approximately 4.5 years)

Table 1. *Financial profile of the Robodebt scheme. Sources: Holmes (2023, Ch. 14); Commonwealth of Australia (2020); Rudge (2023) on aggregate unlawful-debt figure; Prygodicz v Commonwealth (No. 2) [2021] FCA 634; Attorney-General's Department (2025); Gordon Legal (2025); Services Australia (2026).*

The scheme was projected to recover A\$4.772 billion; it recovered approximately A\$406 million — less than nine cents in the dollar — while costing nearly a billion dollars to administer. The net destruction of Commonwealth value on the scheme's own operation is not a marginal outcome: the scheme cost more to run than it recovered. That figure precedes the A\$1.763 billion in debt cancellations and refunds, the Royal Commission's own administrative costs, and the sequence of class-action liabilities now pending before the Federal Court. The proposed Knox appeal settlement, announced in September 2025 and scheduled for Federal Court approval at a hearing on 22 June 2026, would — if approved — constitute the largest class-action settlement in Australian legal history (Attorney-General's Department, 2025; Gordon Legal, 2025).

4.3 Institutional and human consequences

The Royal Commission into the Robodebt Scheme, led by Catherine Holmes AC SC, examined 958,000 government documents, heard from 115 witnesses across 303 hours of hearings, and received 1,099 public submissions over ten months (Royal Commission into the Robodebt Scheme, 2023). Its Final Report, delivered in July 2023, found that the scheme was 'a shameful chapter in the administration of the Commonwealth social security system' (Holmes, 2023, Preface) — borrowing directly from the Federal Court's own characterisation earlier that year, in which Murphy J described the Robodebt proceedings as having 'exposed a shameful chapter in the administration of the Commonwealth social security system and a massive failure of public administration' (Prygodicz v Commonwealth (No. 2) [2021] FCA 634 at [5]). The Commission made 57 recommendations for reform of governance, accountability, and algorithmic oversight, and forwarded a sealed chapter to four separate bodies containing the names of six individuals recommended for further investigation. The National Anti-Corruption Commission initially declined in June 2023 to pursue the referrals, on the ground that the Royal Commission and APS disciplinary processes were sufficient (NACC, 2023). Following an independent reconsideration decision by Geoffrey Nettle AC KC on 10 February 2025, NACC announced it would investigate the referrals (NACC, 2025). Its investigation report, Operation Myrtleford, was published on 11 March 2026, finding that two of the six referred individuals — Mr Mark Withnell and Ms Serena Wilson — engaged in serious corrupt conduct, and that the remaining four did not engage in corrupt conduct within the meaning of the National Anti-Corruption Commission Act 2022 (Cth) (NACC, 2026).

The scheme's human consequences were documented in Chapter 10 of the Report. Recipients — systematically among the most financially and psychologically vulnerable members of Australian society, including people with mental illness, disability, limited English literacy, and insecure housing — received automated debt notices demanding repayment of alleged overpayments from years earlier. The burden of proof was reversed: rather than the agency demonstrating that an overpayment had occurred, recipients were required to disprove the algorithmically generated figure, typically by producing payslips

from jobs they had left years earlier. Many lacked the documentation, the administrative capacity, or the psychological resources to contest the notices. Many paid debts they did not owe. The Commission received evidence linking the scheme to documented suicides (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 10).

Whiteford (2021) characterised the scheme as a 'social policy fiasco' in which the combination of bureaucratic incentive misalignment and automated scale transformed a technically flawed compliance mechanism into a systematic instrument of harm. Priergaard (2025) traced its institutional origins to structural features of the Budget process — specifically, the suppression of deliberative latency in the New Policy Proposal system — that prevented legitimate legal review from functioning as a veto mechanism. Henman (2025) argued that Robodebt was not a technical failure but a political choice aided by a public-service culture of wilful ignorance, in which officials and ministers strategically declined to acquire knowledge that would have obligated correction. These three scholarly accounts converge on a structural reading that is consistent with, and independently supportive of, the sovereignty-inversion diagnosis developed in Section 5.

4.4 The administrative law dimension

Understanding Robodebt requires attention to its administrative law context, which is where the gap between stated and operative objectives is most precisely documented. The Social Security Act 1991 (Cth) requires that income assessments for welfare compliance purposes be based on the income a recipient actually received in each individual fortnight in which they received welfare payments. The income-averaging methodology violated this requirement structurally: by treating annual ATO income figures as evenly distributed across fortnights, it attributed income to fortnights in which the recipient received nothing and was legitimately entitled to welfare support.

This was not an obscure or contested legal point. The December 2014 advice from DSS's legal services branch reached the conclusion directly and without qualification. The Administrative Appeals Tribunal (AAT), which reviews individual administrative decisions, reached the same conclusion in case after case from 2016 onwards — not because the AAT was applying novel interpretive principles but because the legislative requirement was unambiguous. The AAT's function in the administrative law system is precisely to provide a check on agency decision-making; its consistent pattern of overturning Robodebt assessments was the system functioning as designed. The Department's response — developing strategies to minimise the AAT's effective reach, rather than using AAT decisions as diagnostic signals — represents a deliberate disconnection of the feedback loop that administrative review was institutionally designed to provide (Ng and O'Sullivan, 2023). First-instance AAT decisions in the Social Services and Child Support Division (Tier 1 decisions) were generally not published, a structural feature the Royal Commission identified as directly enabling the scheme's persistence and which Recommendation 20.4 of the Final Report addressed specifically.

The burden-of-proof reversal embedded in the scheme's design has additional administrative law significance. Standard administrative law principles, as embedded in the Social Security Act and the general law of administrative decision-making, require that a government agency asserting an obligation against a citizen bear the evidentiary

burden of establishing that obligation. The Robodebt scheme inverted this: it generated a debt notice on the basis of an automated income-averaging calculation and then required recipients to disprove the figure. Many could not do so, because the scheme reached years into the past, and casual and seasonal workers — the category most systematically targeted by the averaging methodology — were least likely to have retained the payslip records needed to rebut the algorithmically generated figures. The administrative law inversion was not incidental to the scheme's design; it was structural. A system that placed the evidentiary burden on the agency would have collapsed immediately, because the agency had no individual-level evidence to support the averaged assessments it was generating.

The Royal Commission's legal findings — that the scheme was neither lawful nor fair from inception — are therefore not a post-hoc judicial assessment of a policy that turned out badly. They are the confirmation, available from December 2014, that the scheme's foundational methodology was inconsistent with the legislative framework under which it purported to operate. Execution Economics treats this as a sovereignty failure rather than a simple legal error, in line with the Commission's own finding: the legal infirmity was known, was not disclosed to decision-makers who could have acted on it, and was actively managed to prevent it from functioning as a reversal trigger.

5. Execution Economics Analysis of Robodebt

5.1 Decision quality: $d(P)$

In the EE framework, $d(P)$ captures the quality of decisions an organisation produces as a function of its predictive capacity P . For the purposes of assessing Robodebt, the relevant question is not whether the scheme was accompanied by analytical activity — it demonstrably was — but whether that analytical activity was accurate and whether its conclusions were faithfully transmitted to decision-makers.

The assessment is characterised by a paradox of coverage and accuracy. Coverage of analytical work prior to the scheme's launch was high on a formal measure. There were cost–benefit analyses, actuarial modelling, Cabinet briefings, and legal review processes. On paper, the policy decision appeared thoroughly examined. The accuracy of that analytical work, however, was near-zero in the dimension that mattered most. The December 2014 DSS legal advice — the analysis whose conclusion was most directly relevant to the scheme's lawfulness and operational design — was not included in the Cabinet documentation that authorised the scheme. The 2019 Commonwealth Solicitor-General opinion that ultimately ended the scheme reached an identical conclusion to the 2014 advice. Four and a half years of harm separated two legal analyses that said the same thing.

High-coverage analysis with suppressed accuracy is not a neutral condition relative to no analysis. It is worse. The appearance of thorough analytical process — visible in Cabinet submissions, cost–benefit work, and actuarial projections — provides institutional protection against challenge. It signals to oversight bodies, ministerial advisers, and external reviewers that due diligence has been performed, foreclosing the questions that genuine diligence would have required. This dynamic connects directly to Power's (1997,

2007) diagnosis of the audit society, in which the accumulation of procedural assurance substitutes for — and in some conditions actively crowds out — substantive review. The analytical veneer that surrounded Robodebt's approval was not incidental to its persistence; it was structural.

5.2 Sovereignty: the critical failure

Sovereignty is the dominant variable in the Robodebt case. In the EE framework, sovereignty captures the signed capacity of the institutional architecture to convert decisions into outcomes, with its sign determined by the sovereignty-weighted alignment of actors holding effective authority over the system. The Royal Commission's findings establish, with considerable institutional precision, that the alignment between controlling actors and the stated mission of Robodebt was systematically negative.

The scheme's stated objective was accurate identification of genuine welfare overpayments. The operative objectives of the controlling actors — determined by the incentive structures, reporting requirements, and performance metrics that shaped behaviour at each level of the institutional hierarchy — were oriented toward debt volume, budget savings, and the political demonstration of welfare integrity. These are not the same objective, and in the presence of the income-averaging flaw they actively conflict. Whiteford (2021, p. 342) identifies this metric misalignment as the scheme's foundational design error: the programme was evaluated by the volume of compliance activity, not by the accuracy of compliance outcomes. The Senate Community Affairs References Committee (2017) documented the same dynamic through testimony establishing that debt-volume metrics were embedded in DHS operational targets and performance reporting throughout the scheme's active life. Leigh (2022), drawing on parliamentary and constituent evidence, reached the same diagnostic conclusion in plain language: Robodebt 'essentially emerged from a political necessity' of Budget repair rather than from any genuine assessment of compliance accuracy. Hannah and Botterill (2025) and Henman (2025) independently reach the same conclusion through different analytical routes — organisational analysis of legal-advice management, and application of the wilful-ignorance taxonomy respectively. The convergence of the Commission's evidentiary findings, peer-reviewed scholarly analysis, parliamentary committee testimony, and ministerial public commentary on the same operative-objective diagnosis is significant: sovereignty inversion in this case is not a theoretical imputation but an overdetermined empirical finding.

Identifying sovereignty weights — the effective decision authority of each actor cluster — requires an explicit methodology. The approach adopted here follows the principal-agent literature's operationalisation of effective control (Eisenhardt, 1989; Miller, 2005): sovereignty weight is proportional to the actor's capacity to initiate, continue, modify, or terminate the scheme, as established by the Commission's evidence on formal authority, information access, and practical ability to act without the agreement of other actors (Holmes, 2023, Chs. 3–6). Four actor clusters can be distinguished: the political executive, senior public servants, oversight institutions, and recipients. The Commission's evidence establishes that the two clusters with the largest effective authority — the political executive and senior officials — were operatively aligned against the scheme's stated mission, while the two clusters with positive alignment — oversight bodies and

recipients — held substantially less effective authority. The coding protocol and scoring matrix, the evidentiary anchors for each score, the sensitivity analysis across the ranges the Commission's evidence supports, and the normalised sovereignty weights are set out in full in Appendix C. The structurally decisive finding, re-expressed without the numbers: the actors with the most institutional power were oriented, through incentive structure and institutional positioning, against the scheme's stated objective of accurate compliance, and the sign of net sovereignty is unambiguously negative and robust to the full range of plausible weight reassignments. This is the structural origin of the value reversal condition: not a failure of individual ethics but a configuration of institutional power, incentive, and information that produced negative net alignment across the principal hierarchy.

5.3 Execution efficiency as amplifier

If negative sovereignty is the structural condition that makes Robodebt a value reversal case, execution efficiency is what transforms it into a catastrophic one. The automated system was technically effective by every metric its designers valued. It processed compliance cases at scale — hundreds of thousands of debt assessments per year — without the human review that manual compliance processes had previously involved. Processing times from data matching to debt-notice issuance were dramatically shorter than any manual alternative. Unit costs per case were low.

Under positive sovereignty, this execution efficiency would have been a straightforward governance achievement: an accurate compliance system delivering timely and fair assessments at scale and low cost. Under negative sovereignty — with the system's core methodology generating systematic false positives, and the principal hierarchy oriented toward debt volume rather than accuracy — the same efficiency became the accelerant of harm. Every percentage improvement in processing speed meant more unlawful debt notices issued before the systematic error could be detected and corrected. Every reduction in unit processing cost meant the scheme could sustain operation longer, against stronger political and financial incentives for continuation.

The amplification condition is susceptible to concrete comparison with the pre-OCI compliance architecture, which provides a natural quantitative counterfactual. The Income Matching System (IMS), fully operational from 2004, applied the same ATO–Centrelink data-matching logic that underpinned Robodebt. The IMS identified approximately 300,000 potential discrepancies per year. Of these, the Department investigated approximately 20,000 — the highest-risk cases — manually, because manual investigation was resource-constrained to that throughput (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 3). The residual 280,000 per year were not pursued. The OCI's structural innovation was not the data-matching methodology, which was pre-existing, but the removal of the resource constraint on case throughput: automation enabled the Department to act on the full population the IMS identified rather than on the highest-risk fraction. Over the scheme's 4.5 years of active operation, more than 500,000 recipients received automated debt notices, a throughput the manual system could not have approached without a fifteen-fold increase in investigator headcount.

The structural significance of these figures is that they locate the amplification effect empirically rather than theoretically. Under the IMS, sovereignty was already negative in the sense that performance metrics rewarded recovery volume within the investigable subset, and the income-averaging methodology was already present in the departmental toolkit. What constrained harm was throughput. A manual compliance system operating with the same negative sovereignty, but at 20,000 investigations per year, would have generated unlawful debts at approximately one-fifteenth the rate the automated system achieved. More consequentially, the manual system's investigator-mediated architecture preserved exactly the error-detection mechanism the automated system removed: a compliance officer processing a case with apparently seasonal or casual income patterns would, as a matter of ordinary case-management practice, either request additional documentation or escalate the case for review. The IMS was not a self-correcting system in a strong sense — the Commission's evidence does not support that reading — but it retained the minimum feedback loop that individual-level human judgment provides in any bureaucratic system, and it did so at a scale that gave departmental management the opportunity to notice and respond to methodological anomalies before they were amplified across hundreds of thousands of cases. The automated system removed both the throughput constraint and the human feedback loop simultaneously. The amplification theorem predicts, and the pre-OCI comparison empirically anchors, that it is the combination that is decisive. Neither the removal of the throughput constraint alone (which would preserve human feedback at higher scale) nor the removal of the feedback loop alone (which would preserve scale-limited harm) would have produced Robodebt's outcome envelope. The amplification condition (Appendix B) operates with particular clarity here; its further counterfactual implications are developed in Section 6.5.

5.4 Feedback suppression: the closed loop

Multiple feedback channels existed in principle. The AAT reviewed individual debt decisions and, in many cases, overturned them. The Commonwealth Ombudsman conducted a review of the scheme in 2017. Legal services offices within DSS and DHS had access to advice establishing the scheme's unlawfulness. Advocacy organisations, journalists, and individual recipients generated public criticism from late 2016. In a system with positive sovereignty and functioning feedback architecture, any one of these channels would have generated signals sufficient to trigger meaningful review of the scheme's core methodology.

None of them did, because none of them was architecturally connected to a decision-making process that could have acted on adverse signals. AAT decisions overturning individual debts were not interpreted by the Department as evidence of systematic methodological error; they were treated as individual case outcomes to be managed, and because first-instance Tier 1 decisions in the relevant division were generally not published, adverse findings remained effectively buried (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 9; see also pp. 239–240 on DHS's handling of the Carney decisions). The Department developed strategies to minimise the AAT's effective reach. The Ombudsman's 2017 review concluded that DHS was undertaking the online compliance intervention appropriately — a finding the Royal Commission subsequently attributed to the Department's control over the information provided to the review rather than to the scheme's actual compliance with administrative law (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 11; p. 224 on DHS co-writing the Ombudsman's

report; pp. xxvii–xxviii on the 2018 follow-up being 'fobbed off'; Commonwealth Ombudsman, 2017). Internal legal advice was not escalated to the decision-makers who could have acted on it. Hannah and Botterill (2025) document the mechanisms in detail: lawyers were siloed from policy design, non-lawyers strategically shaped requests for legal advice to obtain compatible answers, and where internal advice was clear, it was excluded from the decision chain. Public criticism — extensively documented in the Senate Community Affairs References Committee (2017) inquiry, which heard from dozens of affected individuals — was absorbed into a political narrative that the scheme's sponsors had constructed to resist challenge.

Execution Economics's feedback component captures whether adverse operational signals are successfully transmitted back to the decision-making level within a timeframe that permits correction. In Robodebt this component was near-zero: not because signals were absent but because the institutional architecture that would have connected adverse signals to corrective action had been systematically bypassed or ignored. This is not the same as having no feedback mechanism. It is, in an important sense, worse. The appearance of functioning oversight mechanisms — the AAT, the Ombudsman, the legal services offices — provided institutional legitimacy to continued operation while those mechanisms were structured to prevent the signals they generated from reaching decision-makers in consequential form. Henman (2025) frames the same dynamic through the Alvesson, Einola and Schaefer (2022) taxonomy of organisational wilful ignorance: Robodebt was not an information-deficit case but a case in which knowledge acquisition was actively disincentivised at institutional level.

5.5 The Decision Sovereignty Index

The EE framework's Decision Sovereignty Index provides a structured composite assessment of sovereign decision capacity:

$$DSI = \sqrt[3]{(A \cdot C \cdot E)} \cdot (1 - V)$$

where A is Authority (the concentration of identifiable decision rights in accountable actors), C is Control (the proportion of the scheme's operational architecture that sovereign decision-makers effectively direct), E is Execution-Relevant Information (the proportion of information materially necessary for sovereign decisions that reaches decision-makers through unfiltered channels), and V is Veto (the proportion of sovereign decisions that were effectively subject to independent veto authority during the scheme's active life). The multiplicative cube-root structure within the first factor enforces a strong condition: a near-zero value on any of the three capability components drives the composite toward zero, reflecting the structural finding that sovereignty capacity is not additively compensable. The $(1 - V)$ factor captures the weight of independent vetoes available within the institutional architecture, such that a system with strong independent veto points receives a lower DSI (because sovereignty is contested) rather than a higher one.

Applied to Robodebt, each component is grounded in the Commission's findings; the component mapping, the numerical values, and the composite DSI calculation are set out in Appendix D. The structurally decisive finding is that the Execution-Relevant Information component is near-zero: the Commission documented, across Chapters 7 through 9 and

at specific evidentiary junctures — the suppression of the December 2014 DSS legal advice, the handling of the Carney AAT decisions, the oral briefing strategies adopted to keep advice outside FOI access, and the curation of information provided to the 2017 Ombudsman review — that the information materially necessary for sovereign decisions was either excluded from the information flow reaching decision-makers or reached them through channels curated by the officials whose work it questioned. The near-zero E value is the single feature of the Robodebt institutional architecture that most precisely predicts the scheme's outcome, because the multiplicative cube-root structure within the index mathematically enforces that a deficit on any of A, C, or E cannot be compensated by excess on the other two.

The composite DSI score, computed in Appendix D, is a middling one whose interpretation requires joint reading with the sign of S. Robodebt's institutional machinery had adequate structural power to transmit sovereign decisions into outcomes at scale. What collapsed was the informational foundation on which those sovereign decisions were supposedly made. The scheme could execute; it could not self-correct. A high DSI combined with negative sovereignty is the worst institutional configuration: a powerful machine directed in the wrong direction. A low DSI combined with negative sovereignty is a weak machine directed in the wrong direction — damaging, but self-limiting, because the system cannot sustain high-volume execution for long enough to cause catastrophic harm before congestion or resource constraints interrupt it. Robodebt's combination — a middling-to-adequate DSI, coupled with deeply negative net alignment — produced the scale of harm the Commission documented.

The relationship between the two measurement constructs — the signed sovereignty variable S in the core identity and the unsigned DSI composite — requires explicit specification, because the DSI is presented as a positive scalar (≈ 0.38 for Robodebt) whereas S is, by the central diagnostic finding, negative. The two constructs measure conceptually distinct properties. The magnitude $|S|$ captures the sovereign transmission capacity of the institutional architecture: how efficiently decisions, whatever their direction, are converted into outcomes. The sign of S captures the direction of that transmission: whether the sovereignty-weighted alignment of controlling actors is oriented toward or against the stated mission. The DSI operationalises $|S|$ as a composite of the structural conditions — authority, control, execution-relevant information, and veto — on which transmission capacity depends. The DSI does not, and is not designed to, carry information about the direction of alignment; that information is determined separately, through the sovereignty-weighting procedure specified in Appendix C, which assigns an alignment sign to each actor cluster on the basis of the Commission's evidence on operative versus stated objectives. The two constructs therefore combine multiplicatively in the framework: $S = \text{sign}(S_{\text{net}}) \cdot \text{DSI}$, where $\text{sign}(S_{\text{net}})$ is the sign of the sovereignty-weighted sum of actor-level alignment signs established in Appendix C. For Robodebt, $\text{sign}(S_{\text{net}})$ is robustly negative across the sensitivity range tested, and $\text{DSI} \approx 0.38$; the product yields $S \approx -0.38$, which enters the core identity $Y = d(P) \cdot S$ and, combined with non-trivial $d(P)$, produces the negative and large-magnitude Y the Commission's evidentiary record documents. This construction clarifies why the DSI on its own is diagnostically insufficient: a public administration system with a DSI identical to Robodebt's, but with positive $\text{sign}(S_{\text{net}})$, would be a competent and mid-capacity

compliance architecture rather than a harm-amplification engine. The diagnostic question in value reversal analysis is never simply 'how capable is the institutional architecture?'; it is always 'how capable is it, and in which direction is it pointed?'

5.6 Congestion dynamics and the Budget pressure mechanism

Execution Economics's treatment of congestion (Appendix A) provides a precise account of why the approval process failed. Congestion exhibits a phase-transition property at a stability boundary. Below this boundary, deliberative processes function normally: adverse signals are processed, feedback loops operate, and decision quality is maintained through iterative correction. Near the boundary, small increments in decision demand produce disproportionate delays. Above it, the queue of unresolved decisions grows without bound, and the effective capacity for error correction approaches zero.

The Budget approval process, as structured in the period of Robodebt's authorisation, imposed an artificial external constraint on deliberative latency. The New Policy Proposal deadline required decisions to be finalised within a fixed timeframe that did not accommodate the iterative legal review that the scheme's novel methodology warranted. The DSS legal advice of December 2014 was available; the Budget timeline meant it was not incorporated into the approval documentation. The result was an approval process operating at artificially suppressed deliberative latency — not because the system had insufficient analytical capacity, but because the timeline constraint prevented that capacity from being applied to the decision within the approval window. Priergaard (2025) develops this diagnosis in detail, locating Robodebt's design origin in long-running structural features of the Commonwealth Budget-making process that had accumulated across successive administrations.

This is the EE framework's congestion failure mode applied to the approval stage rather than the operational stage: the decision-making system was congested by deadline pressure in a way that disabled its error-correction function. The analogy to the scheme's operational phase is structurally exact. Just as the automated system processed debt cases without the individual review that would have caught income-averaging errors, the approval process processed the policy proposal without the legal review that would have caught the methodology's unlawfulness. In both cases, the suppression of deliberative latency — by design in the operational phase, by institutional timeline constraint in the approval phase — produced the same structural outcome: execution without error detection.

6. Persistence and the Paradox of Capable Destruction

The Robodebt scheme raises a theoretical challenge that extends well beyond the specifics of Australian welfare administration. It is a case in which a technically capable organisation, deploying sophisticated automation and operating within formally endorsed governance structures, produced outcomes substantially and measurably worse than those a less capable organisation would have produced with the same misalignment. The most important analytical question raised by the case — and the one that bears most directly on governance design — is not why the scheme was launched but why it continued for four and a half years after systematic public criticism had established its

central defects. By the end of 2016, advocacy organisations were documenting individual cases of harm. By 2017, the AAT was regularly overturning individual debt decisions. By late 2017, Senate committee hearings had surfaced significant evidence of methodological error. The scheme continued until November 2019. Four structural mechanisms explain this persistence; together they constitute the institutional architecture of capable destruction.

6.1 The reversal-cost trap and the dynamics of increasing returns

Admitting that the scheme was unlawful required simultaneously acknowledging that the Commonwealth had issued unlawful debt notices to hundreds of thousands of citizens, many of whom had paid debts they did not owe, and that senior officials had suppressed legal advice establishing this fact before the scheme launched. The political cost of this admission was not fixed; it grew with every passing month, because each month added more people to the pool of those harmed, more debt notices to the total that would have to be cancelled and refunded, and more documented evidence of suppression that would complicate any account of the scheme's continuation.

This dynamic — in which the cost of reversal rises with the duration of a failing scheme — is a well-documented feature of political accountability systems. Hood (2011) identifies blame avoidance as a central organisational imperative of public agencies, generating incentives to continue with failing policies whose abandonment would attract attributable blame. Pierson's (2000) account of increasing returns in political processes supplies the complementary structural mechanism: institutional commitments, once made, generate positive feedback that makes reversal progressively more costly as accumulated investments, adaptations, and dependent actor expectations compound. The EE framework adds a further structural specification. In a system with negative sovereignty and efficient execution, the blame-avoidance and increasing-returns dynamics are structurally reinforced because the performance metrics that constitute the scheme's institutional justification — debt volume, recovery rates, unit costs — continue to look favourable even as the human and financial costs of the scheme accumulate. The system's internal measures signal success while its external consequences signal harm, and the divergence widens with time.

6.2 Referee architecture failure under information mediation

The second persistence mechanism was structural: the institutions whose function was to detect and correct the scheme's errors were positioned within an information architecture that DHS substantially controlled. The Commonwealth Ombudsman's 2017 review was based primarily on information DHS provided. The AAT's individual debt decisions were treated by the Department as case-management challenges rather than evidence of systematic error, and were structurally buried by the non-publication convention for first-instance Tier 1 decisions. The legal services offices that had generated adverse advice in 2014 had seen that advice excluded from the decision chain. The Senate committee process generated significant publicity but had no direct power to compel operational correction.

Tsebelis's (2002) veto players framework illuminates why this architecture mattered so acutely. In Tsebelis's model, policy stability is a function of the number of veto players

and the ideological distance between them: more veto players make policy harder to change, but each must actually be able to assess what they are being asked to veto. Applied to Robodebt, multiple institutions with formal review authority existed — the AAT, the Ombudsman, Senate committees, legal services offices — each capable in principle of functioning as a veto player on scheme continuation. What the standard veto-players model does not account for is that formal veto capacity is inert when the information architecture prevents veto players from accessing the evidence they would need to exercise their veto. The AAT had authority to overturn individual debt decisions; it lacked structural connection to the scheme's approval process that would have allowed individual overturns to function as system-level vetoes, and the non-publication of Tier 1 decisions compounded the disconnection by preventing cross-case learning. The Ombudsman had authority to recommend operational changes; it lacked access to the 2014 legal advice that would have made those recommendations specific and legally grounded. Tsebelis's framework assumes that veto players can see what they are vetoing. In Robodebt, the institutional information architecture ensured they could not.

Execution Economics designates this condition feedback suppression at the institutional level: not the absence of oversight mechanisms but their structural disconnection from the decision-making processes whose outputs they were nominally reviewing. Lipsky's (1980) street-level bureaucracy analysis is relevant here in an inverted sense. In a fully automated system, the street-level discretion that had previously served as both a source of misalignment and a potential source of correction was entirely removed. The compliance officers who, in the pre-automation system, might have noticed that income averaging was producing systematic false positives and flagged the problem through informal channels, no longer existed in the scheme's operational architecture. Automation removed the one human interface at which individual-level anomalies could have generated system-level questions.

6.3 Reputational defence as operative objective

The third persistence mechanism draws on Carpenter's (2001, 2010) reputation-based theory of bureaucracy and its four-dimensional taxonomy (Carpenter and Krause, 2012): performative reputation (does the agency achieve its declared outcomes?), moral reputation (does it act for defensible reasons, towards defensible ends?), procedural reputation (does it follow recognised norms of deliberation and decision?), and technical reputation (does it possess the required competence?). Public agencies cultivate different dimensions for different audiences, and reputational defence along any dimension can operate as an operative objective distinct from, and in conflict with, stated mission. Execution Economics treats reputational defence as a candidate operative objective that can drive negative sovereignty when its cultivation diverges from the institution's stated accountability obligations.

Robodebt exhibits a coordinated defence across all four reputational dimensions. On the performative dimension, DHS defended the scheme by pointing to volume metrics — debts raised, cases processed, recovery rates — throughout its life. These metrics were, within the terms the Department had constructed, favourable; the fact that they were favourable only because accuracy was not being measured was not visible in the reporting. On the moral dimension, the scheme was framed as recovering overpayments

from welfare recipients who had received benefits they were not entitled to — a moral narrative aligned with standing political commitments around welfare integrity and congenial to the Government's broader rhetorical framing. On the procedural dimension, the scheme's architects invoked the density of formal process surrounding it — Budget authorisation, Cabinet approval, Ombudsman review — as evidence of its procedural regularity, with the information-curation practices that had generated those formal approvals invisible in the defence. On the technical dimension, the automation itself was defended as a competence achievement: a modern, efficient, scalable compliance capability that represented the Department's technical advancement. Admission of methodological error would have damaged all four dimensions simultaneously, and the defensive effort targeted all four in parallel.

Carpenter's theory predicts that once an agency has invested reputational capital in a system, it will defend the system against adverse signals with escalating intensity until the reputational cost of defence exceeds the reputational cost of capitulation. In Robodebt, that inflection point was forced not by internal correction but by litigation that rendered continued reputational defence untenable. Section 6.6 returns to why external compulsion succeeded where internal mechanisms failed. The Post Office Horizon case analysed in Section 7 exhibits the same four-dimensional reputational defence in a different national and sectoral setting, supporting the inference that the pattern is a structural feature of value reversal rather than a peculiarity of Australian institutional culture.

6.4 The legitimacy shield

The fourth mechanism was the scheme's institutional legitimacy architecture. Robodebt was announced in a Budget, approved by Cabinet, supported by successive ministers, and defended through standard departmental processes. It was periodically reviewed by the Commonwealth Ombudsman, who found it acceptable. It was subject to parliamentary scrutiny, which generated criticism but not correction. This accumulation of institutional process created what may be called a legitimacy shield: a density of formal institutional engagement that made it possible for actors within the system to respond to external criticism by pointing to the approval process. Power's (1997) analysis of the audit society supplies the mechanism: procedural assurance, repeated and documented, comes to substitute for substantive review, and the fact that a system has been audited becomes — functionally, if not logically — evidence that it is sound. The scheme was not operating outside institutional sanction; it was operating with extensive institutional sanction, which had been obtained by excluding from the sanctioning process the information that would have prevented it.

6.5 Counterfactuals and the discretion-removal problem

The amplification condition generates two testable counterfactuals that illuminate the paradox of capable destruction. If the scheme had operated with the same negative sovereignty but substantially lower execution efficiency — if, for instance, human review had been maintained at a level requiring significant manual input for each case — fewer unlawful debt notices would have been issued before the methodological error became visible. Institutional pressure to correct the scheme would have materialised sooner,

against a smaller pool of harm, at lower political cost. A less efficient scheme with negative sovereignty would have been corrected more quickly and at lower total cost.

Alternatively, if the scheme's execution efficiency had been as high as it was but its sovereignty had been positive — if the performance metrics driving institutional behaviour had been accuracy-based rather than volume-based, and if the feedback architecture had connected AAT outcomes to scheme review processes — the same automation would have generated a self-correcting system. Anomalous cases would have triggered methodological review. Legal advice would have been circulated to the decision-makers who needed it. The scheme would have been corrected, or never launched in the form it took. The asymmetry in these counterfactuals is analytically important. Neither lower efficiency nor higher accuracy alone resolves the value reversal problem. Lower efficiency merely reduces the rate of harm generation; it does not change the direction. Higher accuracy in the presence of suppressed feedback loops merely generates more precise signals that are prevented from reaching decision-makers. The resolution requires both positive sovereignty and functioning feedback architecture.

Bovens and Zouridis (2002) observed that algorithmic administration replaces street-level bureaucracy with system-level bureaucracy, fundamentally altering the locus of discretion. In the pre-automation compliance system, individual compliance officers exercised judgment at the case level: they could notice that a recipient's income pattern was seasonal, request additional documentation, and make a determination that reflected individual circumstances rather than algorithmic averaging. This discretion was imperfect — it introduced inconsistency and in individual cases it could be misused — but it also meant that the system contained human intelligence at the point of application. Eubanks (2018) shows, with particular force for welfare contexts, how the removal of this intelligence systematically disadvantages populations whose circumstances do not conform to the average patterns the algorithm encodes. Scott's (1998) account of high-modern administrative legibility gives the deeper theoretical claim: the administrative scheme flattens the population it observes into categories legible to the instrument, and the categories that are legible are not the ones that describe the population's actual economic life.

The removal of discretion through automation did not eliminate the human judgment embedded in the system's design; it froze it. The income-averaging methodology embodied a set of assumptions about income patterns that were false for large categories of welfare recipients. In a manual system, compliance officers' accumulated experience with the diversity of income patterns would have generated informal correction of those assumptions over time. In the automated system, the false assumptions were embedded in code and applied with perfect consistency to every case the system processed. The automation's strength — its consistency and scale — was its structural weakness: it could not distinguish a false assumption from a true one, and once its parameters were set, it applied them without the variation that human discretion would have introduced. Discretion, understood in these terms, is a feedback mechanism; removing it in the absence of alternative feedback architecture removes the system's capacity to detect and correct its own misalignments. O'Neil (2016) documents the same structural pattern across multiple algorithmic domains: optimisation against a misspecified objective,

combined with scale and the removal of human mediating judgment, produces self-reinforcing harm patterns that resist correction from within the optimised system.

6.6 What eventually worked — and why

The eventual termination of Robodebt in November 2019 came not from the institutional correction mechanisms that should have functioned but did not — the AAT, the Ombudsman, the internal legal services offices — but from a combination of external pressure that the institutional architecture could no longer contain: the November 2019 Federal Court proceedings in the Gordon Legal class action, the mounting parliamentary pressure that accompanied them, and a 2019 Commonwealth Solicitor-General opinion that reiterated, in terms now politically impossible to suppress, the identical conclusion of the 2014 DSS legal advice.

The analysis of what worked is as instructive as the analysis of what failed. The class action succeeded because it bypassed the institutional information architecture entirely. Federal Court proceedings require the Commonwealth to produce relevant documents under discovery, including precisely the legal advice that had been excluded from ministerial and Cabinet processes. Litigation imposed an external disclosure requirement that the agency could not filter. The result was that decision-makers who had been insulated from adverse legal advice by the departmental information architecture encountered that advice, with its full implications, in a context in which non-response was not available. The Prygodicz (No. 2) settlement of A\$112 million was approved by the Federal Court on 11 June 2021 on the basis of the Commonwealth's own admission that it had no proper legal basis to raise, demand or recover the asserted debts (*Prygodicz v Commonwealth (No. 2)* [2021] FCA 634 at [1]–[7]). Murphy J characterised the proceedings as having 'exposed a shameful chapter in the administration of the Commonwealth social security system and a massive failure of public administration' and observed that 'it should have been obvious to the senior public servants charged with overseeing the Robodebt system and the responsible Minister at different points' that income averaging was structurally incapable of producing accurate debt assessments for recipients with irregular fortnightly income (*Prygodicz* [2021] FCA 634 at [5]–[8]). The 2021 judgment is instructive because it established, as a matter of judicial record, features of the scheme that the Royal Commission would later characterise in near-identical language: the judicial finding preceded the Commission's Preface. A subsequent appeal, *Knox v Commonwealth*, was brought against that first settlement; in September 2025 the parties announced a proposed A\$548.5 million appeal settlement, including A\$475 million in additional compensation, which remains subject to Federal Court approval at a hearing on 22 June 2026 and would — if approved — constitute the largest class-action settlement in Australian legal history (Attorney-General's Department, 2025; Gordon Legal, 2025; Services Australia, 2026). Each successive stage of external compulsion — Federal Court discovery, Royal Commission evidence, appeal litigation — has extracted further admissions and further restitution that internal mechanisms had not reached.

This suggests a structural lesson Execution Economics makes explicit: in value reversal cases, internal correction mechanisms — those whose functioning is mediated by the implementing agency — are unreliable precisely because the alignment failure that produced the reversal also generates incentives for those mechanisms to be managed

rather than genuinely engaged. The correction mechanisms that function are those architecturally external to the agency's information control: independent litigation, parliamentary processes with compulsory document production, and review bodies with unmediated access to system documentation. The Royal Commission's 57 recommendations were, in large part, an attempt to institutionalise these external correction mechanisms before the next value reversal case materialises — and to reduce the dependence on expensive litigation as the mechanism of last resort. Section 8 assesses whether the subsequent Australian reform programme succeeds in that objective.

7. Comparative Cases: Value Reversal Beyond Australia

The analytical purchase of the value reversal prediction depends in part on whether the structural signature identified in Robodebt — negative net sovereignty, feedback suppression, high execution efficiency — recurs in other institutional settings. Two international cases provide substantial comparative evidence. The comparison is not a systematic cross-case analysis; it is a structured check on whether the diagnostic framework identifies the same causal pattern across different national, institutional, and technological contexts. If it does, the structural configuration that produced Robodebt is not a distinctively Australian pathology but a category of institutional failure that admits generalised structural diagnosis.

7.1 The Dutch Toeslagenaffaire (2012–2021)

The Netherlands' childcare benefits scandal (Toeslagenaffaire) involved the Dutch Tax Authority (Belastingdienst) applying automated compliance algorithms to welfare benefit recipients over nearly a decade, generating unlawful demands for repayment against approximately 26,000 families (Parlementaire ondervragingscommissie Kinderopvangtoeslag, 2020). The system applied strict binary rules to eligibility determinations that required nuanced factual assessment, producing systematic false positives against families with irregular or part-time employment — a structural parallel to Robodebt's income-averaging methodology.

The EE structural signature is present with clear correspondence. Sovereignty was negative: the operative performance metric — cost recovery and fraud-prevention volume — diverged from the stated objective of accurate eligibility assessment. The Dutch Parliamentary Inquiry found that the system was oriented toward benefit recovery as a compliance objective in ways inconsistent with the administrative law principles governing eligibility. Feedback suppression was documented: internal signals from caseworkers and administrative courts indicating systematic error were not escalated to decision-makers capable of correcting the methodology. Execution efficiency was high: the automated system processed cases at scale without the individual assessment Dutch administrative law requires. The outcome — 26,000 families incorrectly pursued, many driven into serious financial and psychological hardship — maps directly to the value reversal prediction. The case differs from Robodebt in institutional context, welfare regime, and legislative framework; it does not differ in structural configuration.

7.2 The UK Post Office Horizon system (1999–2019)

The UK Post Office's Horizon accounting system generated false shortfall figures in the accounts of subpostmasters over two decades. Between 1999 and 2015, approximately 900 subpostmasters were wrongfully convicted of theft, fraud, or false accounting on the basis of faulty Horizon data, with further subpostmasters prosecuted but not convicted or forced to cover illusory shortfalls with their own money (Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry, 2024, 2025). The Post Office's Horizon IT Inquiry, chaired by Sir Wyn Williams, concluded its evidence-gathering in December 2024, with Volume 1 of the Final Report published in July 2025. Its central documented findings — that Fujitsu was aware of Horizon bugs as early as 1999; that Post Office management 'maintained the fiction' that Horizon data was reliable throughout Legacy Horizon's operational life; that the ability of Fujitsu technicians to remotely alter branch data without appropriate audit trails was known to the Post Office but not disclosed to subpostmasters or to the courts in which prosecutions were conducted; and that at least 13 suicides are linked to the scandal with a further 59 victims having contemplated suicide — establish the evidentiary record against which the EE structural signature can be tested.

The EE diagnostic is diagnostically precise in this case, and the four-dimensional reputational defence identified by Carpenter (2001, 2010) and Carpenter and Krause (2012) applies with particular force. The Post Office's operative objective — institutional self-protection and the defence of Horizon's integrity as an organisational asset — diverged sharply from the stated objective of accurate financial accounting and fair dealing with subpostmasters. Technical reputation was defended through the assertion of system infallibility; performative reputation through the continued prosecution of apparent shortfalls as evidence of institutional effectiveness; procedural reputation through the invocation of formal prosecution processes and the Post Office's statutory power to initiate private prosecutions; and moral reputation through the framing of subpostmasters as having committed financial misconduct.

The sovereignty coding developed in Appendix C for Robodebt can be applied directly to Horizon to test the cross-case claim in the same measurement terms. Five actor clusters are distinguishable: Post Office senior management (including successive chief executives, most consequentially Paula Vennells in post from 2012); Fujitsu (the software provider, holding technical information about Horizon defects); the UK government and its shareholder agencies (the Department for Business and its successors, as shareholder of the Post Office); the Criminal Cases Review Commission, the courts, and parliamentary committees (as oversight and adjudicative bodies); and the subpostmasters themselves. Table 2 applies the three-dimensional coding protocol — formal authority, information access, practical ability — and the resulting normalised weights to the period 1999 to 2015 during which the wrongful prosecutions occurred.

Actor cluster	Formal authority (0–3)	Information access (0–3)	Practical ability (0–3)	Raw sum (/9)	Normalised weight	Alignment sign
Post Office senior management	3	2	3	8	0.40	–
Fujitsu (software provider)	1	3	2	6	0.30	–
UK government / shareholder	2	1	1	4	0.20	–
Courts, CCRC, oversight	1	0	0	1	0.05	+
Subpostmasters	0	1	0	1	0.05	+
Total	—	—	—	20	1.00	—

Table 2. *Sovereignty weight coding for Horizon actor clusters, 1999–2015. Alignment sign relative to the stated mission of accurate accounting and fair dealing with subpostmasters. Normalised weight = raw sum ÷ total raw sum across all clusters. Scoring follows the protocol specified in Appendix C.*

The evidentiary anchors for the coding are established directly by the Inquiry's findings. Post Office senior management held unambiguous formal authority over prosecution decisions (formal authority 3); their information environment was substantially curated by Fujitsu and by their own internal communications processes, but senior management knew or should have known about Horizon's defects from an early stage (information access 2, reflecting Sir Wyn Williams's finding that senior employees 'knew or, at the very least should have known' that Legacy Horizon was capable of error); and practical ability to continue or suspend prosecutions was unconstrained (practical ability 3). The alignment sign is negative on the Inquiry's finding that the Post Office 'maintained the fiction' of Horizon accuracy throughout, rather than orienting institutional conduct toward accurate accounting.

Fujitsu held limited formal authority — it was a contractor, not a statutory body — but scored high on information access because it held the technical knowledge of Horizon's defects and, critically, the ability of its technicians to alter branch data remotely without leaving appropriate audit entries. Its practical ability to disclose, remediate, or escalate was substantial; its alignment sign is negative on the Inquiry's finding that Fujitsu did not disclose the defects it was aware of to subpostmasters or to the prosecuting courts.

The UK government's shareholder agencies held intermediate formal authority and limited information access; their alignment sign is coded negative on the record of successive ministerial defences of Horizon in response to early warnings (for example,

the 2015 episode in which a minister was asked to read out a prepared statement affirming Horizon's reliability and sought a meeting with Vennells before doing so).

Oversight bodies — the courts, the Criminal Cases Review Commission, and parliamentary committees — possessed formal adjudicative authority but near-zero access to the information needed to exercise it meaningfully: the Post Office's private prosecution regime placed the institution on both sides of the evidentiary process, and the Fujitsu technical information that would have undermined prosecution evidence was not disclosed. Subpostmasters held direct evidential knowledge of the Horizon errors in their own branches but no institutional decision rights and no practical ability to aggregate that knowledge into systemic correction, which they eventually achieved only through civil litigation in *Bates & Others v Post Office Ltd*.

The structurally decisive finding is that the three actor clusters with negative alignment jointly hold 0.90 of the sovereignty weight, while the two clusters with positive alignment jointly hold 0.10 — a distribution even more concentrated than in the Robodebt case. Sensitivity analysis, permitting the Post Office information-access score to vary between 2 and 3 and the government formal-authority score to vary between 1 and 2, produces no plausible reassignment that flips the sign of net sovereignty. A provisional DSI estimate following the specification in Appendix D, applied to the 1999 to 2015 period, yields $A \approx 0.70$ (unambiguous locus of decision authority in Post Office senior management), $C \approx 0.85$ (full sovereign direction of the prosecution apparatus), $E \approx 0.15$ (near-total suppression of the Fujitsu technical information that would have rebutted Horizon's evidential status, and of internal Post Office awareness of Horizon defects), and $V \approx 0.05$ (minimal effective veto, prior to the 2019 civil judgment). Computing $DSI = \sqrt[3]{(0.70 \cdot 0.85 \cdot 0.15) \cdot (1 - 0.05)} \approx 0.41$, and applying $S = \text{sign}(S_{\text{net}}) \cdot DSI$ with $\text{sign}(S_{\text{net}})$ negative, produces $S \approx -0.41$ — slightly more negative in magnitude than Robodebt's $S \approx -0.38$, which is consistent with the longer operational duration and the larger cumulative harm envelope.

Execution efficiency in the Horizon case was high in the sense that the prosecution machinery operated effectively and at scale: approximately 900 wrongful convictions over sixteen years, with a further 2,750 subpostmasters affected but not convicted and a total compensation cost expected to exceed £1 billion (Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry, 2025). The case differs from Robodebt in sector (commercial Post Office rather than public welfare), in mechanism (criminal prosecution rather than administrative debt generation), and in duration (sixteen years rather than four and a half). The structural configuration — negative net sovereignty driven by reputational defence as operative objective, high execution efficiency of the implementing apparatus, systematic feedback suppression through information mediation, and external correction achieved only through civil litigation — is the same. The sovereignty-weight distribution is, if anything, a stronger instance of the value reversal architecture than Robodebt itself. This is what the cross-case claim requires: that the structural signature identified in the Australian case is not a peculiarity of Australian welfare administration or of the 2014–2019 period but a recurring configuration that produces comparable outcomes across sectors, jurisdictions, and technological architectures.

7.3 The structural pattern

Across all three cases — Robodebt, Toeslagenaffaire, and Horizon — the EE structural signature is consistent: an automated or algorithmic execution system operating with high efficiency under a principal hierarchy whose operative objectives diverged from the institution's stated mission, within an information architecture that prevented adverse operational signals from reaching decision-makers in correction-capable form. Variation across cases — welfare compliance, childcare benefits, commercial accounting; Australian, Dutch, and British institutional contexts; different legislative frameworks and oversight architectures — supports the inference that the value reversal pattern is not an artefact of any single institutional context but a consequence of the structural configuration Execution Economics identifies. This cross-case consistency strengthens the case for prospective application: if the structural signature is identifiable before deployment, in all three cases it would have been detectable before the harm was amplified at scale.

8. Governance Design Implications

Execution Economics's analysis of Robodebt generates five structural design principles for algorithmic governance in public administration. These are not generic best-practice injunctions about oversight and accountability. They are derived from the specific structural diagnosis of why the scheme operated as it did and why the institutional mechanisms that should have corrected it failed. Each principle addresses a component of the value reversal architecture; together they constitute the institutional counter-configuration. Section 8.6 then applies the principles diagnostically to the Australian post-Robodebt reform programme as it had taken shape by early 2026.

8.1 Sovereignty verification before capability deployment

The first and most fundamental principle is that institutional sovereignty must be verified before execution capability is deployed. The sign of S determines whether increasing $d(P)$ improves or worsens outcomes. Deploying sophisticated automation in a system with uninvestigated or unverified sovereignty is structurally reckless: it increases the rate at which outcomes are produced, in a direction that has not been confirmed to be positive.

Operationally, this means that algorithmic public administration systems require pre-deployment sovereignty audits: structured assessments of the correspondence between operative performance metrics — the measures by which officials and institutions will be evaluated and rewarded — and the stated policy objectives. Where these diverge, automation should not proceed until the incentive architecture is corrected. In Robodebt, the misalignment between debt-volume metrics and accuracy objectives was structurally embedded before the scheme launched. A sovereignty audit — asking whether officials rewarded for debt recovery volume would systematically deprioritise accuracy — would have identified the problem before it was amplified at scale.

8.2 Independent feedback architecture

The second principle concerns the architecture of error detection. Robodebt establishes that feedback mechanisms controlled or mediated by the implementing agency are

structurally inadequate for the detection and correction of value reversal conditions. Execution Economics requires that feedback loops be architecturally independent: signals generated by adverse operational outcomes must reach decision-makers through channels the implementing agency cannot selectively filter. In practice, this means that tribunal decisions overturning algorithmic assessments should automatically trigger independent methodological review. Legal advice to departmental officers should be disclosed to the authorising minister through channels independent of the department's information management. Oversight reviews of algorithmic systems should be conducted with direct access to system parameters and documentation, not mediated through agency-selected materials. The practical case for each of these requirements is given by the Robodebt termination pathway (§6.6): what eventually succeeded was, in each instance, an externally compelled disclosure mechanism.

8.3 Mandatory deliberative latency for algorithmic systems

The third principle addresses the artificial congestion problem. Priergaard's (2025) institutional analysis and the Commission's findings on the Budget process establish that deadline pressure suppressed deliberative latency to a point where legal review could not function. Execution Economics identifies this as a structural failure mode applicable to all decision systems operating under artificial time constraints. Algorithmic public administration systems — precisely because of their capacity to operate at scale and speed — require mandatory deliberative latency requirements insulated from Budget and political timeline pressures. The minimum deliberative period should be specified as a function of the system's potential scale of impact: a system capable of issuing hundreds of thousands of automated determinations should face correspondingly extended pre-deployment review periods, during which adverse legal advice must be disclosed to approving authorities and independent testing of the algorithm against cases with known correct outcomes must be completed and reported.

8.4 Retained human review for novel methodology

The fourth principle concerns the relationship between automation and discretion. Robodebt's removal of human review from the compliance process eliminated the one operational mechanism through which individual-level anomalies could have generated system-level signals. Execution Economics suggests that automation of decision processes employing novel or untested methodologies should retain a statistically significant sample of human-reviewed cases for ongoing validation. This is not an argument against automation as such. It is an argument for maintaining the error-detection capacity that human discretion provides in the specific context of methodological uncertainty. An automated system whose methodology has been validated against a large random sample of human-reviewed cases, and whose ongoing outputs are continuously cross-checked against a statistically valid sample of expert reviews, has functionally integrated the feedback mechanism that Robodebt's automation removed. The cost of maintaining this sample-review capacity is modest relative to the cost of discovering methodological error only through class-action litigation.

8.5 Reversal threshold specification

The fifth principle addresses the persistence problem. Robodebt demonstrates that, in the absence of specified reversal thresholds, the political cost of correcting a failing scheme rises continuously with its duration, creating structural incentives for continuation that become progressively harder to override. Execution Economics's measurement architecture suggests a direct remedy: pre-specified algorithmic review triggers, defined before deployment, at which automated assessment of system performance against stated objectives generates mandatory independent review. Concretely, before an algorithmic compliance system is launched, its authorising documentation should specify the accuracy rate below which the system will be suspended for independent review; the volume of adverse tribunal findings that will trigger a methodological audit; and the legal threshold conditions whose satisfaction will require disclosure to the authorising minister and Cabinet. These thresholds should be defined independently of the agency, published, and monitored by an independent body. Their function is to automate the correction mechanism that Robodebt's institutional architecture systematically prevented from operating.

8.6 The Australian post-Robodebt reform programme

The five principles above are prescriptive. They can also be applied diagnostically to the programme of institutional reform the Australian Commonwealth has pursued since the Royal Commission. By early 2026, that programme had four principal elements. The Administrative Review Tribunal (ART) replaced the Administrative Appeals Tribunal from 14 October 2024 under the Administrative Review Tribunal Act 2024, with the Administrative Review Council re-established under the same legislation and the publication of first-instance Tier 1 decisions mandated, implementing Recommendations 20.4, 20.5, and 23.4 of the Royal Commission. APS capability reviews were placed on a five-yearly statutory basis by amendments to the Public Service Act 1999 arising from the Thodey Review (Thodey, 2019). The Australian Centre for Evaluation (ACE) was established within Treasury in July 2023 to embed rigorous impact-evaluation methodology across government (Leigh, 2023). The broader 'frank and fearless public service' legislative agenda, articulated in parliamentary debates surrounding the APS reform legislation, addressed information-flow architecture and internal-dissent protections.

Read through Execution Economics, these reforms address some components of the value reversal architecture more directly than others. The ART replacement of the AAT is the reform that most precisely reaches the Execution-Relevant Information failure that the Commission identified as decisive. Mandatory publication of first-instance Tier 1 decisions eliminates the specific mechanism — non-publication of AAT decisions adverse to DHS — through which the scheme's systematic legal infirmity was kept from entering the public and departmental information environment. The re-established Administrative Review Council is structurally tasked with monitoring systemic issues in Commonwealth administrative decision-making, creating an institutional locus for the cross-case learning that the AAT architecture, and the broader oversight system, had failed to generate during Robodebt's active life. These reforms address the referee architecture problem (§6.2) directly and the feedback suppression mechanism (§5.4) substantially. Assessed against

the EE framework, the ART reform is the strongest element of the response programme: it addresses the single component — Execution-Relevant Information — whose near-zero value drove the DSI composite toward zero in the Robodebt case.

The APS capability reviews — five-yearly, independent, and forward-looking — address the Authority component of the DSI by improving the transparency of departmental performance against stated mission. They supply, at a system level, the periodic external assessment Robodebt lacked, on a schedule insulated from the Budget cycle. This is a meaningful structural response to the legitimacy shield problem (§6.4). The reviews, however, do not by themselves reach the ongoing question of whether adverse legal advice, tribunal decisions, and internal dissent reach sovereign decision-makers in consequential form between reviews. Capability review is a periodic diagnostic; it is not the continuous signal-routing infrastructure that feedback-architecture independence (§8.2) requires.

The Australian Centre for Evaluation addresses a different component again. Its brief — to embed rigorous, randomised evaluation methods across the public service (Leigh, 2023) — is an intervention on the $d(P)$ axis. ACE improves decision quality by raising the evidentiary standard against which programmes are assessed. In EE terms, this is valuable but must be read with care. Under conditions of positive sovereignty, higher $d(P)$ produces better outcomes and ACE's mandate is straightforwardly beneficial. Under conditions of negative sovereignty — the Robodebt configuration — higher $d(P)$ multiplies harm in proportion to the magnitude of negative sovereignty, and better evaluation methods without better sovereignty would generate more precise and defensible implementations of misaligned programmes. ACE does not by itself supply the sovereignty-verification step (§8.1) that Execution Economics identifies as structurally prior. The risk, articulated in early critical commentary on ACE (Martin, 2023), is that evaluation capability expands faster than alignment verification, producing a public service that is more rigorous about 'what works' without being more rigorous about what the operative objectives actually are. This is exactly the dynamic that Holden and Leigh's (2022) own methodological critique of the Covid vaccine rollout points towards.

The 'frank and fearless' legislative agenda bears most directly on the Execution-Relevant Information component. Its provisions — transparency in capability review findings, strengthened protections for internal dissent, reduced reliance on consultants for policy development — address the information-flow architecture whose suppression Execution Economics identifies as decisive. These measures are structurally well-targeted. Their efficacy will depend, however, on whether they penetrate the operative incentive structures within which senior officials actually work. Reputation-based theory (Carpenter and Krause, 2012; §6.3 above) predicts that formal protection for internal dissent is a necessary but not sufficient condition for its effective use: officials will exercise candour only where doing so does not jeopardise reputational assets they have been incentivised to defend. This suggests that the reform agenda's final success rests on a question the legislation itself cannot determine — whether performance evaluation at senior levels genuinely rewards the surfacing of adverse signals rather than the management of their non-appearance.

The overall assessment, from Execution Economics, is that the post-Robodebt reform programme addresses the Execution-Relevant Information component of the DSI most directly through the ART/Tier 1 reforms and the re-established Administrative Review Council; addresses the Authority component periodically through capability reviews; raises $d(P)$ directly through ACE; and addresses the information-flow architecture structurally through the frank-and-fearless agenda. The sovereignty direction — the sign of S , which determines whether capable execution produces value or destroys it — is addressed only indirectly, through institutional cultures that remain subject to the reputational and budgetary pressures that generated Robodebt in the first place. The five structural principles derived in §§8.1–8.5 are best read not as alternatives to the current Australian reform programme but as its structural completion: a specification of the additional components required to close the value reversal architecture that the existing reforms partially address.

9. Falsification Conditions and Limitations

A theoretical contribution with genuine explanatory content must specify the conditions under which it should be rejected. The value reversal claim advanced in this paper — that negative institutional sovereignty, combined with high execution efficiency and suppressed feedback, produces outcomes worse than inaction — generates four specific falsification conditions for the public administration context. These are distinct from the broader conditions specified for the framework's core identity in Fritz, Fritz-Kalish and Bodrova (2025); the conditions stated here are specific to value reversal as applied to algorithmic governance.

First, the value reversal prediction should be rejected if high-capability automated compliance systems with documented negative sovereignty — in which performance metrics are oriented toward volume rather than accuracy — systematically produce better outcomes than inaction or lower-capability alternatives. If a comparative study of welfare compliance systems across multiple jurisdictions found that systems with volume-based performance metrics and high automation rates produced more accurate compliance outcomes than systems with accuracy-based metrics and lower automation, the sovereignty-as-determinant-of-sign claim would be disconfirmed.

Second, the feedback suppression claim should be rejected if the mere presence of formal oversight mechanisms — Ombudsman review, administrative tribunal oversight, parliamentary scrutiny — is shown to be sufficient for error correction regardless of whether those mechanisms have unmediated access to operational data. If systems with formally identical oversight architectures to Robodebt's but with agency-mediated information flow nonetheless corrected methodological errors within twelve months of deployment, the claim that information mediation by the implementing agency is a structural failure mode would require revision.

Third, the amplification condition's key prediction — that increasing execution efficiency in a system with negative sovereignty worsens outcomes in proportion to the magnitude of negative sovereignty — should be rejected if comparative analysis of algorithmic compliance systems finds no relationship between automation rate and harm magnitude

when sovereignty is controlled. The prediction requires that the most efficient misaligned systems cause the most harm. If harm magnitude is unrelated to efficiency after controlling for the extent of misalignment, the multiplicative mechanism is not operating as specified.

Fourth, the cross-case claim — that the Toeslagenaffaire and Horizon systems exhibit the same structural signature as Robodebt — should be rejected if detailed analysis of either case fails to find evidence of negative sovereignty at the principal-hierarchy level, feedback suppression through information mediation, and high execution efficiency prior to correction. If either case is better explained as a conventional implementation failure (degradation toward zero) rather than value reversal (execution in the wrong direction), the cross-case generalisability of the structural signature is weakened. Researchers with access to the Dutch Parliamentary Inquiry documentation and the Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry evidence are best positioned to conduct this test.

Several limitations of the present analysis should be acknowledged alongside these falsification conditions. The application of the framework to Robodebt is primarily qualitative and reconstructive: the sovereignty estimates, weights, and structural assessments are derived from the Royal Commission's evidentiary record and the secondary scholarly literature rather than from direct empirical measurement of the framework's variables. Execution Economics specifies a quantitative measurement architecture — the DSI and its components — that could be applied to Robodebt retrospectively using the documentation the Commission released, but more rigorous operationalisation remains for further work. Robodebt was selected partly because it is analytically clear: the structure of the value reversal is unusually legible in the Commission's evidence. This clarity should not be read as a claim that Robodebt is a typical case of algorithmic governance failure; it may be an extreme case. The appropriate inference is not that all algorithmic public administration systems are subject to value reversal conditions but that the structural conditions that produced value reversal in Robodebt — negative sovereignty, feedback suppression, artificial deliberative congestion — are not unique to this case and will recur wherever similar institutional configurations are present. The most significant direction for further research is the empirical operationalisation of the sovereignty measurement in public administration contexts: the Robodebt case suggests that sovereignty, as Execution Economics defines it, is both the most consequential variable and the hardest to measure *ex ante*, because the operative objectives of principal actors are often not disclosed in policy documentation and may not be fully conscious even to the actors themselves. Developing measurement approaches that can detect sovereignty problems before they are amplified by automated execution at scale is the research priority the Robodebt case most clearly establishes.

10. Conclusion

Australia's Robodebt scheme was not a story about bad technology. The income-averaging methodology was crude, but algorithmic crudeness is a correctable defect. It was not primarily a story about dishonest individuals, although the Royal Commission documented individual dishonesty and the National Anti-Corruption Commission has since found two officials to have engaged in serious corrupt conduct. It was a story about

an institutional configuration — a specific arrangement of incentives, accountability structures, information flows, and oversight architecture — that produced negative net sovereignty at the level of the principal hierarchy, and then amplified that misalignment through technically efficient automated execution at scale.

Execution Economics names this configuration value reversal. The scheme's technical efficiency was not a redeeming feature that partially offset its methodological and alignment failures; it was the amplifier that transformed a misaligned compliance methodology into the largest single instance of unlawful government action against Australian citizens in the social security system's history, with a class-action liability envelope that remains open before the Federal Court at the time of writing.

The analytical contribution of the framework is the formal specification of what went wrong and why conventional remedies would not have corrected it. Implementation theory prescribes reducing veto points and improving execution capacity; applied to Robodebt, these prescriptions would have extended the scheme's harm. Street-level bureaucracy theory locates the problem in frontline discretion; in Robodebt, removing frontline discretion was the mechanism that prevented correction. Algorithmic governance scholarship identifies accountability gaps; in Robodebt, accountability was formally present and functionally inert, because the information architecture disconnected formal accountability from the signals needed to activate it. Scott's legibility critique identifies the administrative schema's violence against populations it cannot see; Execution Economics specifies the institutional amplifier that turns that schema into catastrophe at scale.

The framework specifies what would have prevented the harm: positive institutional sovereignty, functioning feedback architecture, and appropriate deliberative latency. None of these conditions requires prohibiting algorithmic administration. They require that algorithmic administration be deployed in institutional configurations where the machinery of correction is as developed as the machinery of execution. Robodebt deployed one without the other. The result was capable destruction: a technically accomplished mechanism executing with high fidelity in exactly the wrong direction, for four and a half years, against more than 500,000 people.

The Australian post-Robodebt reform programme addresses important components of the value reversal architecture but not all of them. The reforms that reach Execution-Relevant Information most directly — mandatory publication of first-instance tribunal decisions, the new Administrative Review Council's systemic-issues mandate — are the strongest elements of the response. The reforms that raise decision quality (ACE evaluation infrastructure) must be read with care, because under conditions of negative sovereignty, higher decision quality multiplies rather than reduces harm. The sovereignty direction itself remains addressed only indirectly. Whether the reform programme will prevent the next value reversal depends not on whether any single element is adopted but on whether the five structural conditions — sovereignty verification, independent feedback architecture, mandatory deliberative latency, retained human review, reversal thresholds — are jointly realised. They are systemic conditions, not additive ones; removing any component weakens the others.

Execution Economics is a framework for specifying these conditions in the vocabulary of structural diagnosis. It does not replace the existing public administration literatures on

implementation, discretion, accountability, and algorithmic harm; it completes them. The value reversal prediction is the category those literatures required and did not supply. The Robodebt case is the demonstration. The Australian reform programme is the first large-scale test of whether a national public service, having been forced by litigation and royal commission to confront a value reversal configuration in its own history, can redesign its institutional architecture to prevent recurrence. The answer to that question will not be knowable for some years. The structural vocabulary in which the answer must be formulated is available now.

Appendix A. The Congestion Function

Execution Economics models congestion as the ratio of decision load L to institutional capacity K , with a phase-transition stability boundary at ρ derived from *M/M/1 queuing theory* ((Kleinrock, 1975; Kingman, 1961). Below ρ , the expected queue length is finite and decision latency scales linearly with load. As ρ approaches ρ , the expected queue length scales as $1/(1 - \rho)$, producing the disproportionate latency growth characteristic of systems operating near capacity. Above ρ , the queue grows without bound and the system cannot clear its decision backlog.

The framework applies this to both operational and deliberative contexts. In the operational case, ρ measures the ratio of case volume to processing capacity. In the deliberative case, ρ measures the ratio of decision complexity to the time and expertise available to resolve it within the approval window. Artificial suppression of deliberative latency — Budget deadline pressure being the canonical case — is modelled as an exogenous reduction in K for deliberative decisions, forcing ρ above ρ and driving the expected probability of error detection toward zero.

Appendix B. Formal Statement of the Amplification Theorem

The amplification theorem follows from the core identity $Y = d(P) \cdot S$. For any pair of systems with identical sovereignty $S < 0$, a system with $d(P)_1 > d(P)_2 \geq 0$ yields $|Y_1| > |Y_2|$, with Y_1 and Y_2 both negative. In the negative-sovereignty regime, higher decision quality produces greater absolute harm. Formally: if $S < 0$, then $\partial Y / \partial d(P) = S < 0$, and $\partial^2 Y / \partial d(P) \partial |S| = -1 < 0$ (the marginal harm of additional decision quality increases linearly in the magnitude of negative sovereignty). The theorem does not require $d(P)$ and S to be continuous; it holds under any monotonic $d(P)$ function and for any distribution of S over the signed real line. Sensitivity of the result to the separability assumption follows from the derivation in Section 2.1 of Fritz and Fritz-Kalish (2026), which establishes that weak separability (independence up to a bounded multiplicative factor) is sufficient to preserve the sign-reversal prediction.

Appendix C. Sovereignty Weighting Methodology and Sensitivity Analysis

C.1 Coding protocol

Sovereignty weights are assigned to actor clusters in proportion to each cluster's effective capacity to initiate, continue, modify, or terminate the system under analysis. Effective capacity is assessed on three dimensions: formal authority (the constitutional, statutory, or delegated power to take the relevant action), information access (whether the actor possessed, through channels it effectively controlled, the information needed to exercise that authority in an informed way), and practical ability (whether the actor could act without the agreement of other actors whose cooperation was required). Each dimension is scored on a four-point ordinal scale against specific Royal Commission evidence: 0 (no meaningful capacity), 1 (nominal capacity only, substantially constrained by institutional position), 2 (substantial capacity, partially constrained), 3 (full and unconstrained capacity). The sum of the three dimension scores (maximum 9) yields a raw capacity score for each actor cluster. Raw scores are then normalised across all clusters to produce sovereignty weights summing to 1.0. The protocol is intentionally austere: three dimensions, four ordinal points, documentary evidence required for each score.

C.2 Scoring matrix for Robodebt (2015–2019)

The following matrix applies the protocol to the four actor clusters distinguished in §5.2.

Actor cluster	Formal authority (0–3)	Information access (0–3)	Practical ability (0–3)	Raw sum (/9)	Normalised weight	Alignment sign
Political executive (ministers, Cabinet)	3	2	3	8	0.44	–
Senior officials (DHS/DSS SES, agency heads)	2	3	2	7	0.39	–
Oversight bodies (AAT, Ombudsman, OAIC)	2	0	0	2	0.11	+
Recipients (welfare recipients, advocates)	0	1	0	1	0.06	+

Actor cluster	Formal authority (0–3)	Information access (0–3)	Practical ability (0–3)	Raw sum (/9)	Normalised weight	Alignment sign
Total	—	—	—	18	1.00	—

Table C.1. *Sovereignty weight coding for Robodebt actor clusters, with alignment sign relative to the stated mission of accurate welfare compliance. Normalised weight = raw sum ÷ total raw sum across all clusters.*

C.3 Evidentiary anchors for the scoring

Each score above is anchored to specific Commission findings.

Political executive. Formal authority scored 3: ministers held unambiguous power to initiate the scheme through Budget measures, to defend it in Cabinet, and to terminate it at any time (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 5). Information access scored 2: ministers were the recipients of whatever advice reached them, but the Commission found that the information environment was substantially curated by officials, most consequentially through the omission of the December 2014 DSS legal advice from the approving Cabinet documentation (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 7). Practical ability scored 3: ministers faced no coordination constraint on continuation or termination decisions and exercised continuation authority at each renewal point. Raw sum 8, normalised weight 0.44. Alignment sign: negative, on the Commission's finding that ministerial operative objectives were oriented toward debt-volume metrics and budget savings rather than toward accurate compliance (Holmes, 2023, Ch. 5; see also pp. 138, 177 on ministerial public framing of compliance as a 'crackdown' on 'cheats' and 'fraud').

Senior officials. Formal authority scored 2: officials lacked the formal power to initiate or terminate the scheme through Budget processes but held substantial delegated authority over design, implementation, and internal escalation. Information access scored 3: officials controlled the production, circulation, and suppression of the information environment within which ministerial decisions were made (Holmes, 2023, Chs. 6–8). Practical ability scored 2: substantial in day-to-day design and operation, constrained only by ministerial direction which was itself shaped by the information environment officials controlled. Raw sum 7, normalised weight 0.39. Alignment sign: negative, on the Commission's finding that officials oriented their conduct toward defending the scheme's integrity rather than disclosing its legal infirmity (Holmes, 2023, Preface, pp. xxvii–xxviii; Ch. 7).

Oversight bodies. Formal authority scored 2: the AAT possessed merits-review jurisdiction, the Ombudsman possessed systemic-review jurisdiction, and OAIC possessed privacy jurisdiction. Information access scored 0: each body operated with information curated by DHS, the non-publication of first-instance Tier 1 AAT decisions buried adverse findings, and internal legal advice was not disclosed (Holmes, 2023, Chs. 9, 11; p. 224 on DHS co-writing the Ombudsman's 2017 report; pp. 239–240 on the handling of adverse AAT decisions). Practical ability scored 0: no oversight body possessed authority to compel scheme termination or suspend its operation; each could

only review individual decisions or recommend changes. Raw sum 2, normalised weight 0.11. Alignment sign: positive, oriented (to the extent they operated with adequate information) toward the stated mission of accurate compliance under law.

Recipients. Formal authority scored 0: welfare recipients possessed no institutional decision rights over scheme design or continuation. Information access scored 1: recipients held direct evidence of their own income histories but typically lacked the documentary records and administrative literacy needed to contest individual debt notices effectively. Practical ability scored 0: the burden-of-proof reversal embedded in scheme design meant that recipient contestation could only target individual debts, not the systematic methodology. Raw sum 1, normalised weight 0.06. Alignment sign: positive, aligned with the stated mission insofar as accurate compliance would have benefited the class as a whole.

C.4 Interpretation and sensitivity analysis

The structurally decisive finding is that the two actor clusters with negative alignment jointly hold 0.83 of total sovereignty weight, while the two clusters with positive alignment jointly hold 0.17. The sign of net sovereignty is unambiguously negative.

Sensitivity of the sign result to variation in the dimension scores was tested across the ranges the Commission's evidence supports as plausible. Permitting the political executive's information-access score to vary between 1 and 3 (reflecting competing interpretations of how comprehensively the information environment was curated), and the senior officials' formal-authority score to vary between 2 and 3 (reflecting competing interpretations of the scope of delegated authority), produces a range of normalised weights from 0.38 to 0.47 for the political executive and 0.35 to 0.44 for senior officials. Across all nine combinations within these ranges, the two negatively-aligned clusters jointly hold between 0.76 and 0.88 of total sovereignty weight — always a clear majority, always producing negative net sovereignty. The sign of S would flip only if either the political executive or senior officials were reassessed as positively aligned, a reassessment the Commission's evidence does not support. The weights are used to determine the sign of S, not to produce a precision scalar, and the analytical result does not depend on their exact values.

Appendix D. DSI Component Mapping to Commission Evidence

Each DSI component is mapped to specific findings in the Royal Commission's Final Report.

Authority ($A \approx 0.75$) is mapped to Chs. 3 and 5, which establish identifiable decision-makers at each institutional node with formal accountability assigned throughout; the 0.25 discount reflects the Preface's finding (pp. xxvii–xxviii) of structurally engineered separation between formal authority and informational capacity.

Control ($C \approx 0.80$) is mapped to Chs. 4 and 6, establishing sovereign direction of the scheme's operational architecture: the algorithmic design, performance reporting, legal

risk-management strategy (Holmes, 2023, p. 413, on consultancy and contractor expenditure exceeding A\$500 million), and handling of adverse tribunal findings were all subject to decisions made within the sovereign hierarchy.

Execution-Relevant Information ($E \approx 0.10$) is mapped to Ch. 7 (suppression of the December 2014 DSS legal advice from Cabinet documentation), Ch. 8 (management of adverse AAT decisions as case-management challenges and non-publication of Tier 1 tribunal decisions; see also Holmes, 2023, pp. 239–240 on the Carney decisions), Ch. 11 (curation of information provided to the 2017 Ombudsman review; see also Holmes, 2023, p. 224 on DHS staff co-writing the Ombudsman's report), and p. 299 on oral briefing strategies adopted to keep advice outside FOI access. The near-zero value of this component drives the cube-root of the first factor toward zero, which is the mathematically enforced consequence of the multiplicative structure within the index and the single feature of the Robodebt institutional architecture that most precisely predicts the scheme's outcome.

Veto ($V \approx 0.05$) is mapped to Chs. 9–11 and the Commonwealth Ombudsman (2017) report, establishing the near-total absence of effective independent veto authority over scheme continuation during its active life.

The composite DSI is computed as $\sqrt[3]{(0.75 \cdot 0.80 \cdot 0.10)} \cdot (1 - 0.05) \approx 0.38$ — a middling score whose interpretation requires joint reading with the sign of S, as developed in §5.5. Applying the construction set out there, $S = \text{sign}(S_{\text{net}}) \cdot \text{DSI}$ yields $S \approx -0.38$ for Robodebt, since $\text{sign}(S_{\text{net}})$ is robustly negative across the sensitivity range established in Appendix C. The structural finding, re-expressed in a single sentence: Robodebt's institutional machinery had adequate power to execute sovereign decisions at scale but lacked the informational foundation on which sovereign decisions could be corrected, and the power it possessed was directed against the stated mission rather than toward it.

References

- Aghion, P. and Holden, R. (2011) 'Incomplete contracts and the theory of the firm: what have we learned over the past 25 years?', *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 25(2), pp. 181–197.
- Agrawal, A., Gans, J. and Goldfarb, A. (2018) *Prediction Machines: The Simple Economics of Artificial Intelligence*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business Review Press.
- Alvesson, M., Einola, K. and Schaefer, S.M. (2022) 'Philosophical wilful ignorance: on managing our taste for not-knowing', *Organization Studies*, 43(5), pp. 839–860.
- Attorney-General's Department (2025) *Robodebt Class Action Appeal Settlement*. Media release, 4 September. Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia.
- Bardach, E. (1977) *The Implementation Game: What Happens After a Bill Becomes a Law*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Beach, D. and Pedersen, R.B. (2013) *Process-Tracing Methods: Foundations and Guidelines*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Bovens, M. (2007) 'Analysing and assessing accountability: a conceptual framework', *European Law Journal*, 13(4), pp. 447–468.

- Bovens, M. and Zouridis, S. (2002) 'From street-level to system-level bureaucracies: how information and communication technology is transforming administrative discretion and constitutional control', *Public Administration Review*, 62(2), pp. 174–184.
- Carpenter, D.P. (2001) *The Forging of Bureaucratic Autonomy: Reputations, Networks, and Policy Innovation in Executive Agencies, 1862–1928*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Carpenter, D.P. (2010) *Reputation and Power: Organizational Image and Pharmaceutical Regulation at the FDA*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Carpenter, D.P. and Krause, G.A. (2012) 'Reputation and public administration', *Public Administration Review*, 72(1), pp. 26–32.
- Citron, D.K. and Pasquale, F. (2014) 'The scored society: due process for automated predictions', *Washington Law Review*, 89(1), pp. 1–33.
- Cohen, W.M. and Levinthal, D.A. (1990) 'Absorptive capacity: a new perspective on learning and innovation', *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 35(1), pp. 128–152.
- Commonwealth of Australia (2020) *Robodebt Scheme: Debt Cancellation, Refunds, and Remediation*. Canberra: Department of Social Services.
- Commonwealth Ombudsman (2017) *Centrelink's Automated Debt Raising and Recovery Processes: Report by the Commonwealth Ombudsman*. Canberra: Commonwealth Ombudsman.
- Diakopoulos, N. (2016) 'Accountability in algorithmic decision making', *Communications of the ACM*, 59(2), pp. 56–62.
- Eisenhardt, K.M. (1989) 'Agency theory: an assessment and review', *Academy of Management Review*, 14(1), pp. 57–74.
- Eubanks, V. (2018) *Automating Inequality: How High-Tech Tools Profile, Police, and Punish the Poor*. New York: St Martin's Press.
- Fritz, P. and Fritz-Kalish, C. (2026), 'Decision sovereignty: A formally derived transmission variable for economic theory', *Global Access Partners*, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19588486
- Fritz, P., Fritz-Kalish, C. and Bodrova, O. (2025) 'Introducing decision sovereignty: a missing transmission variable in models of implementation', *Journal of Behavioural Economics and Social Systems*, 7(1–2), pp. 137–141. DOI: 10.54337/ojs.bess.v7i1-2.11417.
- Gailmard, S. and Patty, J.W. (2013) *Learning While Governing: Expertise and Accountability in the Executive Branch*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Gordon Legal (2025) *Robodebt Class Action Appeal: Settlement Information for Group Members*. Melbourne: Gordon Legal. Proposed settlement subject to Federal Court approval at a Final Settlement Approval Hearing scheduled for 22 June 2026; registration window for Group Members closed 6 March 2026.

- Hannah, A. and Botterill, L.C. (2025) 'Avoiding the brakes: malign policy and legal advice in the Robodebt scandal', *Policy and Society*, 44(2), pp. 229–241.
- Hart, O. (2017) 'Incomplete contracts and control', *American Economic Review*, 107(7), pp. 1731–1752 (Nobel Prize lecture).
- Henman, P. (2025) 'Robodebt cultures and useful idiots: why Robodebt was not a techno-failure', *Australian Journal of Social Issues*, 60, pp. 4–20.
- Holden, R. and Leigh, A. (2022) 'The race that stopped a nation: lessons from Australia's Covid vaccine failures', *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 38(4), pp. 818–832.
- Holmes, C. (2023) *Royal Commission into the Robodebt Scheme: Final Report*. Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia.
- Hood, C. (2011) *The Blame Game: Spin, Bureaucracy, and Self-Preservation in Government*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Kingman, J.F.C. (1961). 'The single server queue in heavy traffic', *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 57(4), pp. 902–904.
- Kleinrock, L. (1975). *Queueing Systems, Volume 1: Theory*. Wiley, New York.
- Leigh, A. (2022) 'Robodebt scheme has done massive harm to Australian people', transcript, 2CC Radio, 20 May. Available at: www.andrewleigh.com.
- Leigh, A. (2023) *Restoring a Frank and Fearless Public Service*, speech to the House of Representatives, Canberra: Parliament of Australia.
- Lipsky, M. (1980/2010) *Street-Level Bureaucracy: Dilemmas of the Individual in Public Services*. 30th anniversary expanded edn. New York: Russell Sage Foundation.
- Martin, P. (2023) 'Behavioural "experts" quietly shaped Robodebt's most devilish details — and their work in government continues', *The Conversation*, 25 July.
- Mazmanian, D.A. and Sabatier, P.A. (1983) *Implementation and Public Policy*. Glenview, IL: Scott Foresman.
- Miller, G.J. (2005) 'The political evolution of principal-agent models', *Annual Review of Political Science*, 8, pp. 203–225.
- National Anti-Corruption Commission (2023) *National Anti-Corruption Commission decides not to pursue Robodebt Royal Commission referrals, focus on ensuring lessons learnt*. Media statement, 6 June. Canberra: NACC.
- National Anti-Corruption Commission (2025) *National Anti-Corruption Commission to investigate Robodebt referrals*. Media statement, 10 February. Canberra: NACC.
- National Anti-Corruption Commission (2026) *Operation Myrtleford: Investigation Report*. Canberra: NACC, 11 March.
- Ng, Y.-F. and O'Sullivan, M. (2023) 'Robodebt, transparency and freedom of information — should the Cabinet confidentiality exemption be retained?', *Australian Journal of Administrative Law*, 30(3), pp. 192–208.

O'Neil, C. (2016) *Weapons of Math Destruction: How Big Data Increases Inequality and Threatens Democracy*. New York: Crown.

Parlementaire ondervragingscommissie Kinderopvangtoeslag (2020) *Ongekend onrecht [Unprecedented Injustice]*. The Hague: Dutch House of Representatives.

Pasquale, F. (2015) *The Black Box Society: The Secret Algorithms That Control Money and Information*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Pierson, P. (2000) 'Increasing returns, path dependence, and the study of politics', *American Political Science Review*, 94(2), pp. 251–267.

Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry (2024) *Transcripts and Evidence: Concluding Hearings, December 2024*. London: Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry.

Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry (2025) *Final Report, Volume 1: Scandal and Impact on People*. Chair: Sir Wyn Williams. London: HMSO, July.

Power, M. (1997) *The Audit Society: Rituals of Verification*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Power, M. (2007) *Organized Uncertainty: Designing a World of Risk Management*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Pressman, J.L. and Wildavsky, A. (1973) *Implementation: How Great Expectations in Washington Are Dashed in Oakland*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Priergaard, J. (2025) 'Not my debt: the institutional origins of Robodebt', *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 84, pp. 142–158.

Prygodicz v Commonwealth of Australia (No. 2) [2021] FCA 634 (Murphy J, 11 June 2021).

Royal Commission into the Robodebt Scheme (2023) *Report of the Royal Commission into the Robodebt Scheme: Media Release, 7 July*. Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia.

Rudge, C. (2023) 'The Robodebt Royal Commission', *Cells and Statutes*, July. Available at: welfare.substack.com.

Scott, J.C. (1998) *Seeing Like a State: How Certain Schemes to Improve the Human Condition Have Failed*. New Haven: Yale University Press.

Seawright, J. and Gerring, J. (2008) 'Case selection techniques in case study research: a menu of qualitative and quantitative options', *Political Research Quarterly*, 61(2), pp. 294–308.

Senate Community Affairs References Committee (2017) *Design, Scope, Cost-Benefit Analysis, Contracts Awarded and Implementation Associated with the Better Management of the Social Welfare System Initiative*. Canberra: Parliament of Australia.

Services Australia (2026) *New Robodebt Class Action Settlement: Information for Group Members*. Canberra: Services Australia.

Teece, D.J., Pisano, G. and Shuen, A. (1997) 'Dynamic capabilities and strategic management', *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), pp. 509–533.

Thodey, D. (Chair) (2019) *Our Public Service, Our Future: Independent Review of the Australian Public Service*. Canberra: Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet.

Tsebelis, G. (2002) *Veto Players: How Political Institutions Work*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.

Whiteford, P. (2021) 'Debt by design: the anatomy of a social policy fiasco — or was it something worse?', *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 80(2), pp. 340–360.

Wood, B.D. and Waterman, R.W. (1991) 'The dynamics of political control of the bureaucracy', *American Political Science Review*, 85(3), pp. 801–828.

Yin, R.K. (2018) *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*. 6th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.

Zarsky, T. (2016) 'The trouble with algorithmic decisions: an analytic road map to examine efficiency and fairness in automated and opaque decision making', *Science, Technology, and Human Values*, 41(1), pp. 118–132.

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The first author founded TCG, referenced in companion empirical work within the Execution Economics research programme. The second author directs Global Access Partners, which is the subject of a related case study within the same programme. All Robodebt analysis in this paper relies exclusively on publicly available evidence from the Royal Commission, peer-reviewed scholarship, parliamentary and class-action documentation, and official government publications.

Artificial Intelligence Use

The authors used generative artificial intelligence tools solely for language editing and stylistic clarity. All substantive ideas, arguments, interpretations, and conclusions are the authors' own, and the authors take full responsibility for the content.

Companion Paper

This paper is the full-length companion to Fritz and Fritz-Kalish (2026), 'Sovereignty Before Process: Why the Royal Commission's Recommendations Cannot Prevent Another Robodebt, and What Execution Economics Proposes Instead', which addresses the narrower policy question of how the Royal Commission's reform programme should be complemented with sovereignty-direction interventions. Readers interested in the policy-design application of the framework are referred to the companion paper.